

A Technosignature Search for
Extraterrestrial Intelligence Around
25 Eclipsing Exoplanets Selected
from the *Transiting Exoplanet
Survey Satellite* Catalogue.

Rebecca Barrett

MSc (Astrophysics)

School of Health, Engineering, and Sciences
University of Southern Queensland

October 2022

SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS
OF THE AWARD OF MASTER OF SCIENCE

Abstract

In this study, I analyzed the archival data of a subset of 25 eclipsing *Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (TESS)* Targets of Interest (TOIs) for artificially generated radio signals, or ‘technosignatures’, that would indicate the presence of a technologically advanced civilization. Target observations were made by Breakthrough Listen (BL) using the CSIRO Parkes 64-m radio telescope, Murriyang, coupled with the Ultra-wide Low frequency (UWL) receiver (704–4032 MHz). Each target was observed in a cadence consisting of several 5-minute back-to-back source and reference observations for comparison during data analysis. The observational data for each target was processed by compute nodes located at the Parkes Observatory into high frequency resolution data files for analysis. The archival data of each target observation was analyzed through the Breakthrough Listen Data Center (BLDC) using the TURBOSETI dedoppler search code for narrowband signals with a minimum signal to noise (S/N) ratio of 10, minimum drift rate of ± 0.1 Hz/s, and maximum drift rate of ± 4.0 Hz/s. Of the 1,954,880 narrowband signals flagged during analysis, 14,639 passed automated radio interference filters, and were subsequently plotted as a set of 14,639 stacked spectrograms or waterfall plots. Each plot was visually inspected for a signal of interest; all events were attributable to terrestrial Radio Frequency Interference (RFI). While no technosignatures were detected, our data suggests that fewer than 5.31% of observed TOIs have putative narrowband transmitters operating above an equivalent isotropic radiated power of $8.9486 \times 10^{14}W$; the first statistical limit on hypothesised technosignatures during exoplanetary eclipses.

Certification of Thesis

The ideas, experimental work, analysis results, software and conclusions reported in this thesis are entirely my own, except where otherwise acknowledged. The material in this thesis has not been submitted, either in whole or in part, for a degree at this or any other university.

Rebecca Barrett

Rebecca Barrett
(Author)

The work in this thesis is, to the best of my knowledge and belief, the original work of Rebecca Barrett, except as acknowledged in the text. The material in this thesis has not been submitted, either in whole or in part, for a degree at this or any other university.

Brett Addison

Brett Addison
(Principal Supervisor)

Andrew Maxwell

Andrew Maxwell
(Secondary Supervisor)

Danny Price
(External Supervisor)

Chenoa Tremblay
(External Supervisor)

James Green
(External Supervisor)

Acknowledgements

I'd like to thank my project supervisors: Brett Addison, Andrew Maxwell, Chenoa Tremblay, James Green, and Danny Price for investing their professional and personal time in myself and this research project. I have immense appreciation for the regular feedback, discussions, and routine encouragement provided by all parties.

To Danny Price and Andrew Siemion, I extend my immeasurable gratitude for the opportunity to travel to the Breakthrough Listen headquarters at the University of California, Berkeley. This was a life-changing experience that has set me down an incredible and exciting pathway.

I'd also like to acknowledge Breakthrough Listen System Administrator Matt LeBofsky for his aid in migrating and converting the data files necessary for this project to succeed, and for troubleshooting assistance as I learned to navigate the Breakthrough Listen Data Centre.

Dedication

This thesis is dedicated to the memory of Bart Wlodarczyk-Sroka; the space oddity who had an irreversible effect on my mind, and my heart.

I will always be grateful that our world lines intersected.

I'll hunt aliens for the both of us.

Contents

Abstract	ii
Certification of Thesis	iii
Acknowledgements	v
Dedication	vi
List of Tables	x
List of Figures	xii
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Historical Background	2
1.1.1 The Search for Extraterrestrial Intelligence	2
1.1.2 The Breakthrough Listen Initiative	4
1.2 Research Question	5
1.2.1 Why Narrowband?	6
1.2.2 Why Drifting?	6
1.2.3 Why <i>TESS</i> TOIs?	6
1.2.4 Why Secondary Transits?	8
1.2.5 Why Parkes Data?	8
1.3 Structure	9
2 Background	11
2.1 Literature Review	11
2.1.1 Targets of Interest	12

2.1.2	Past Observations	13
2.1.3	Observing Techniques	14
2.1.4	Analysis Pipelines	14
2.1.5	Areas for Further Research	15
2.2	Data Sets	16
2.2.1	List of Observed Targets	16
2.2.2	Target Observations	17
2.2.3	Target Data Files	20
2.2.4	Target System Information	20
2.3	Simulated Signal of Interest	22
3	Methodology	24
3.1	Resources & Software	24
3.1.1	Online Services	24
3.1.2	Computer Services	25
3.1.3	Software	25
3.2	Target Selection	26
3.3	List of Targets	28
3.4	Data Analysis	28
3.4.1	TURBOSETI Hit Search	33
3.4.2	TURBOSETI Event Search & Plot	34
3.4.3	Dynamic Spectra Inspection	35
4	Results	38
4.1	Results of TURBOSETI Analysis	38
4.2	Visual Analysis	40
4.2.1	Clear Examples of RFI	40
4.2.2	Notably Ambiguous RFI	43
5	Discussion	44
5.1	Figures of Merit	45
5.1.1	Equivalent Isotropic Radiated Power	45
5.1.2	Continuous Waveform Transmitter Figure of Merit	47
5.1.3	Drake Figure of Merit	48

5.1.4	Recent Study Comparison	49
5.2	Research Question	51
6	Conclusions	52
6.1	Future Work	53
	References	54
	Appendix	60

List of Tables

2.1	BL TOIs: Target Selection	12
2.2	BL TOIs: Observed & Analyzed	13
2.3	Truncated List of Targets Observed by BL using the Parkes Radio Telescope	18
3.1	<i>TESS</i> TOIs that Underwent Secondary Transit During Parkes Ob- servations	29
5.1	A Comparison of the Figures of Merit with <i>TESS</i> SETI Studies Published in 2022.	50
1	Observed Secondary Transit <i>TESS</i> TOI System Information	63
2	Individual Target TURBOSETI Results & Figures of Merit	64

List of Figures

1.1	Spectra showing local sources of RFI that consistently affect the Parkes UWL bandpass (Hobbs et al., 2020). The UWL receiver records two polarizations which are represented as two different colors, red and blue.	7
1.2	A diagram depicting signal interruption due to secondary transit. As the exoplanet passes behind — and is eclipsed by — its host star, any signal being transmitted from the surface of the exoplanet would cease until it re-emerges from the other side, where the signal would then resume.	10
2.1	A diagram depicting the flow of data during GBT/Parkes and APF observations/analysis. blc = compute node, bls = storage node, blpd = public data node. (Lebofsky et al., 2019).	15
2.2	BL Parkes Data Analysis Pipeline. Frequencies spanning 704 – 4032 HZ are captured by the Parkes UWL receiver, where the raw voltage data are split amongst 26 compute nodes (blc). Processing produces high frequency resolution data files which are analysed using the TURBOSETI pipeline to produce a set of files for each target.	19
2.3	Four histograms illustrating the distribution of exoplanet orbital periods [top left], effective exoplanet temperatures [top right], exoplanet radii [bottom left], and stellar distances [bottom right] amongst the list of 25 eclipsing <i>TESS</i> TOIs.	21
2.4	Example narrowband drifting signal interrupted by secondary transit. Created using SETIGEN (Brzycki et al., 2022).	22

3.1	A skymap pinpointing the location of every <i>TESS</i> TOI observed by BL using the Parkes radio telescope (white plus symbols). <i>TESS</i> TOI that underwent secondary transit during observation are labeled and circled in green. This figure was created using the ALADIN SKY ATLAS.	31
3.2	TURBOSETI Analysis Pipeline	33
3.3	Example Waterfall Plots from Past Studies	36
4.1	A histogram showing the distribution of hits (narrowband signals above a S/N ratio of 10 with drift rates lying between ± 0.1 and $\pm 4.0 Hz/s$) and events (hits present in all related ON-source cadences) found during TURBOSETI analysis.	39
4.2	Four waterfall plots exhibiting several types of RFI regularly encountered during visual inspection of TURBOSETI output. Figure (a) features two prominent narrowband signals: one with a linear drift rate evolution and one sinusoidal. Figure (b) presents a set of 7 narrowband signals at quite a noisy frequency; 6 linear and 1 sinusoidal in drift pattern. Figure (c) is quite busy, with one wider curved signal accompanied by several diagonal signals of varying strength. Figure (d) features a very narrow signal whose drift rate pattern varies over time. For an explanation on the likely origins of each signal and their respective shapes, see Section 4.2.	42
4.3	Two waterfall plots exhibiting the ambiguous RFI events encountered during visual inspection of TURBOSETI output. Figures (a) and (b) both show one narrowband signal with a diagonal drift rate evolution. Both signals are prominent in all ON-source cadences, yet either carry over into, or are slightly visible in, the OFF-source (<i>_R</i>) cadences.	43

Chapter 1

Introduction

It is becoming impossible to ignore the deafening silence from the Universe that surrounds us.

Are we alone?

An age-old question brimming with curiosity and existential angst claws at the back of scientific and creative minds alike; manifesting itself in rich and fantastical science fiction, and theoretical and experimental hypotheses. The Universe we inhabit is unfathomably vast, spanning approximately 28.4 billion parsecs¹. It is home to at least 6×10^{22} stars, each of which host an average of one planet (Westby & Conselice, 2020); alas, we only know of *one* ‘pale blue dot’ that is host to complex, intelligent, and technologically capable life: Earth.

We are still discovering new forms of life on our own planet (Ohara et al., 2022), and until we can cast an equally inquisitive gaze toward the cosmos, we remain ignorant to a Universe that may be teeming with other intelligent life. Rapid advancements in technology and science over the last century have shifted our cosmological perspective, one that drives us toward a less anthropocentric future. Presently, scientific investigations into the presence of extraterrestrial intelligence in our Universe is tightly linked to our technological capabilities, relying heavily on advancements in telescope sensitivity and — of course — funding.

¹Calculation based on Halpern & Tomasello (2016)’s estimated radius of the observable universe, 14,200 Mpc.

1.1 Historical Background

The idea of intelligent extraterrestrial beings has been alive for millennia; from ancient cave paintings around the globe to the relatively recent — and dis-proven (Evans & Maunder, 1903) — misinterpretation of ‘canals’ on Mars. In the latter part of the previous century, the search for advanced extraterrestrial life has transitioned from a mere thought experiment into a potentially quantifiable and scientifically sound endeavour. Our brief historic journey starts with Giuseppe Cocconi and Phillip Morrison whom, in their 1959 paper “Searching for Interstellar Communications” (Cocconi & Morrison, 1959), ponder the existence of technologically capable extraterrestrial societies. Should these technologically advanced civilizations wish to communicate, particularly with planet Earth, what form would such communication take?

Cocconi & Morrison suggest that the primary method used for long distance communication here on Earth, electromagnetic radiation, is the only plausible means by which to bridge interstellar & intergalactic distances. Light is the fastest, information-rich form of communication known to exist thus far. At any point in time, Earth’s atmosphere is ablaze with light that is imperceptible to the human eye — transmitting an invisible cacophony of signals that encode our collective consciousness — a result of decades of advancement in radio communication technology. While radio is not the only waveband to consider when it comes to communication via electromagnetic waves, Cocconi & Morrison conclude that the most promising frequency for interstellar/intergalactic communication would lie within the radio portion of the electromagnetic spectrum, as radio waves penetrate the interstellar medium and Earth’s atmosphere with relatively minimal scattering. This seminal paper led to what we now know as SETI (the Search for Extraterrestrial Intelligence), a subdivision of astronomy concerned with the search for extraterrestrial intelligence.

1.1.1 The Search for Extraterrestrial Intelligence

Experimental SETI began in 1960 with the preparation of Frank Drake’s ‘Project Ozma’ (Drake, 1961). As it happens, Drake had independently come to the

same conclusions as Cocconi & Morrison. As part of Project Ozma, Drake observed nearby stars Tau Ceti and Epsilon Eridani using the 21-cm receiver at Green Bank’s 85-foot single-dish Howard Tatel radio telescope. A moment of excitement turned to disappointment — a theme that follows SETI into the 21st century — when a potential signal turned out to originate not from Epsilon Eridani, but a high-flying plane unknown to the general public at the time (Drake, 1979). Nonetheless, project Ozma sparked the beginnings of an annual scientific meeting centered around the discussion of SETI. The first of these meetings was conducted in 1961, resulting in the famous ‘Drake Equation’, which estimates the average number of actively transmitting extraterrestrial societies in our Milky Way Galaxy. The Drake Equation is as follows:

$$N = R_* \times f_p \times n_e \times f_l \times f_i \times f_c \times L$$

where R_* is the birth-rate of stars conducive to life, f_p is the fraction these stars that host planets, n_e is the average number of habitable planets per star, f_l is the fraction of habitable planets on which life arises, f_i is the fraction of life-supporting planets which harbour intelligent life, f_c is the fraction of said planets with a technologically advanced civilization, and L is the average time over which these civilization can communicate (Drake, 1965; Shostak, 2021).

Over time, advances in technology have facilitated the constraint of parameters such as f_p and n_e (Westby & Conselice, 2020) with optical space telescopes such as *Kepler* (Borucki et al., 2010) and *TESS* (Ricker et al., 2014) contributing to the discovery of hundreds of small, Earth-sized rocky exoplanets. Yet the Drake equation is clearly dominated — at this stage — by unquantifiable parameters: f_l , f_i , f_c , and L . The Drake equation may be one of the only equations in the history of humankind whose main objective is not to be solved, but to motivate inquisitive minds to answer the equally terrifying yet intoxicating question, that is: *are we alone?* The speculation that surrounds each argument is what drives the discussion and subsequent investigation that lies at the heart of SETI (Shostak, 2021).

In 1975, SETI was working its way into mainstream science with Project Cyclops, a Stanford/NASA fellowship program with the aim of designing equipment capable of detecting signals of extraterrestrial origin (Oliver, 1973). Unfortunately, funding was cut due to the objections of a single US Senator in 1981. Funding was again reinstated in 1983, followed by a decade of political roadblocks that — once again — resulted in a cut to funding and subsequent project termination (Tarter, 2001). Thus began the era of private funding. SETI is now funded predominantly through private donations and philanthropy (Tarter et al., 2010), the proceeds of which facilitate the founding and continued operation of SETI science initiatives such as Breakthrough Listen.

1.1.2 The Breakthrough Listen Initiative

The Breakthrough Listen (BL) Initiative² was announced on July 20, 2015 by world renowned physicist Stephen Hawking and science and technology philanthropist, Yuri Milner. BL is a \$100 million, 10 year scientific effort to conduct the most comprehensive astronomical search for extraterrestrial intelligence in history (Worden, 2016; Enriquez et al., 2017a).

The science goals of BL are as follows (Worden et al., 2017; Isaacson et al., 2017; Lacki et al., 2021):

- To perform a sensitive targeted search of the nearest stars at radio, near-infrared and optical frequencies.
- To search for both optical and near-infrared laser emission, and continuous narrow-band emission over a wide range of frequencies.
- To survey 1 million stars at a shallow range of radio frequencies.
- To search several hundred nearby galaxies at radio and optical frequencies.
- To perform a complete radio survey of our Galactic Plane.
- To explore potential observing opportunities at other frequencies.

²Accompanied by several other Breakthrough Initiatives: <https://breakthroughinitiatives.org/>

- To follow-up on promising external sources.

My decision to focus on research with BL stems from a deep rooted interest in the fields of SETI, radio astronomy, and a tremendous opportunity to access BL facilities and resources in collaboration with affiliated supervisors. The work produced in this project will contribute to the collective effort being made to understand our place in the Universe: by investigating a subset of data acquired by BL over the past several years for artificial radio signals that may indicate the presence of an advanced extraterrestrial civilization.

1.2 Research Question

There is no ‘correct’ approach to answering such a question as “are we alone?” We cannot yet — and may never — grasp the reasoning behind our own existence, let alone an existence in isolation. It is only in the last half-century that we have been able to start approaching this problem scientifically; turning what was once wild speculation into methodical practice. Rapid advancement in humanity’s technological capabilities has brought about an influx of exoplanetary discoveries, and with it, an increased interest in the search for life — advanced or otherwise. The discovery of life beyond Earth, or lack thereof, may just be the humbling experience we need to appreciate and look after the planet we inhabit.

From telephones to television, Earth has been leaking artificial electromagnetic radiation into space for over a century; and while this radiation may be weak in strength, it has now travelled far enough to surpass numerous nearby star systems. In this study, I was particularly interested in searching for artificial radio signals from exoplanetary systems that would indicate the presence of a technologically advanced civilization not unlike our own. To accomplish this, a research question was designed that would place limits on such a search, allowing for a targeted and thorough investigation. The research question for this dissertation is as follows:

“Are there radio technosignatures hidden within past Breakthrough Listen Parkes observations? A search for narrowband drifting signals

around *TESS* TOIs undergoing secondary transit.”

1.2.1 Why Narrowband?

Narrowband signals are tonal in nature, defined as spanning frequencies of a few Hz or less. Signals of this bandwidth do not have any *known* astrophysical origin (Tarter, 2001); and much like all narrowband signals produced here on Earth, are likely to be a signal produced artificially using technology. The detection of such a signal — henceforth referred to as a technosignature — originating from outer space would therefore either infer the existence of a technologically advanced extraterrestrial civilisation capable of producing such a signal, or an astrophysical process that we are yet to understand. These are both incredibly exciting prospects.

1.2.2 Why Drifting?

Any narrowband signal originating from outer space would be expected to exhibit a drift in frequency over time, as measured from a fixed position on the surface of Earth (Sheikh et al., 2019). This Doppler shift is caused by the relative motions of the transmitting and receiving bodies as they move through space. Narrowband signals that have drift rates (measured in Hz/s) of zero are a result of local RFI. This type of RFI originates from devices such as mobile phones and internet routers, and tends to flood observations at a set of very particular frequencies (see Figure 1.1). Whilst a signal from a distant system would be expected to have a non-zero drift rate, there are also local sources of drifting RFI that originate from moving objects such as satellites and airplanes.

To distinguish between sources of RFI and a potential technosignature, signals are localized to the target by comparing target and reference observations (the details of this process are explored in Section 2.1.3).

1.2.3 Why *TESS* TOIs?

As previously mentioned, *TESS* is an optical space telescope whose mission was to detect transiting exoplanets in a 2 year all sky survey (Ricker et al., 2014).

Figure 1.1: Spectra showing local sources of RFI that consistently affect the Parkes UWL bandpass (Hobbs et al., 2020). The UWL receiver records two polarizations which are represented as two different colors, red and blue.

Having launched in April 2018, the *TESS* mission has been extended and continues its mission to this day, exceeding all expectations with a catalogue of 5908 exoplanetary candidates³ as of October 2022.

Earth-like exoplanets are a prime target in the search for technosignatures, as we know that life can arise, evolve, and flourish under a very particular set of conditions. Rocky exoplanets also provide the natural resources required to develop technology, as is evidenced in our own technological innovations and continuous advancements here on Earth. Whilst there are other extensive exoplanetary catalogues from predecessor missions such as *Kepler* (Borucki et al., 2010), *TESS* has surveyed an area approximately 400 times larger with a resolution about 10 times greater than that of *Kepler*; focusing on stellar targets up to 100 times brighter and closer (Ricker et al., 2014) allowing for extreme follow-up and characterization of any exoplanetary discoveries. In humanity’s search for extraterrestrial life — intelligent or otherwise — it is imperative that we search as many stellar

³*TESS* Project Candidates: <https://exoplanetarchive.ipac.caltech.edu/cgi-bin/TblView/nph-tblView?app=ExoTbls&config=TOI>

systems as possible; and *TESS* casts the widest net available thus far.

1.2.4 Why Secondary Transits?

A transit describes the orbital motion of one astrophysical body in front of another. For a transit event to occur, the orbital plane of the target system must be oriented approximately along the observer’s line of sight⁴, so that as one body passes in front of the other — perhaps a planet in front of a star — a portion of the stars light is blocked. This periodic dip in brightness is the main process that allows astronomers to identify and analyze exoplanets orbiting other stars. It is reasonable then, when considering game theory, to suggest that another intelligent civilisation *may also* favor the observation of mutually transiting systems, and *may also* conclude that the transmission/receipt of a signal toward/from said systems would be strategically advantageous for the purpose of mutual detection and communication (Kerins, 2021).

There are several orbital positions during an exoplanetary transit that may be considered interesting to another civilization — as they are to us — which lie at the beginning, middle, and end of the transit event. These points may, again, be considered strategically advantageous, and are dubbed ‘Schelling points’. In this project, I have focused on observing two exoplanetary transit Schelling points as each exoplanet begins (passes the point of ingress) and concludes (passes the point of egress) secondary transit (see Figures 1.2). By focusing on targets undergoing secondary transit, I have been able to explore the idea of signal interruption due to exoplanet occultation, and constrained the set of observed targets to be analyzed to a subset that fits the scope of a Masters by coursework dissertation.

1.2.5 Why Parkes Data?

BL have performed most of their radio observations to-date using two single dish radio telescopes located in their respective hemispheres: the CSIRO Parkes 64-m radio telescope, Murriyang (Jeffery, 1964), located in New South Wales, Australia (32.9986 deg S, 148.2621 deg E); and the 100m Green Bank Telescope (GBT, Hall

⁴Note: exoplanets with highly eccentric orbits can still potentially transit their host stars, yet may not undergo secondary transit or vice versa.

& King, 1992) located in West Virginia, USA (38.4330 deg N, 79.8397 deg W). Extensive observations have been made using both telescopes, with a particular focus on the analysis of GBT data (Franz et al., 2022; Traas, 2022). This project has made use of a set of previously unpublished Parkes observations encompassing dates between 2020 February 15 and 2022 April 06 inclusive.

1.3 Structure

The rest of this thesis is organised as follows: Chapter 2 provides background information where Section 2.1 discusses past BL publications in the context of a literature review, introducing the ideas, concepts and methods that will be utilized throughout this investigation; Section 2.2 introduces the data sets and types that will be used throughout the project accompanied by a short discussion on target system parameters; and Section 2.3 provides an example of an idealistic signal of interest. Chapter 3 details the project method, where Section 3.1 introduces the resources and software utilized throughout the project; Section 3.2 presents the process by which the original target list was reduced to produce the final list of targets; Section 3.3 discusses the final list of targets; and Section 3.4 details the data analysis process. Chapter 4 presents the results of the project, where Section 4.1 focuses on the results of TURBOSETI analysis; and Section 4.2 on the results of visual analysis. Chapter 5 pursues further discussion of results, with the calculation of several metrics for comparison to future and past studies in Section 5.1; and Section 5.2 relating the results back to the overarching research question. This thesis concludes with Chapter 6, wherein the research question, method, results, and areas for further investigation are emphasised in Section 6.1.

Figure 1.2: A diagram depicting signal interruption due to secondary transit. As the exoplanet passes behind — and is eclipsed by — its host star, any signal being transmitted from the surface of the exoplanet would cease until it re-emerges from the other side, where the signal would then resume.

Chapter 2

Background

Two all-consuming questions, ever-present at the edge of the inquisitive mind: “Why are we here?” and “Are we alone?”. The latter has a definitive answer, which may, in and of itself, lead to answering the former. The philosophical, technological and scientific implications of making contact with an extraterrestrial civilization; the potential for cultural unification and rapid technological and scientific advancement (Harrison, 2011; Baum et al., 2011) certainly justifies studies into SETI — past, present and future.

To undertake a technosignature SETI study of my own, I first needed to familiarize myself with this particular area of study by reviewing past relevant technosignature SETI publications, the results of which are presented below.

2.1 Literature Review

This literature review provides an overview of the current state-of-the-art technosignature searches. Given that BL is by far the largest SETI program in recent history, a particular focus is given to BL publications. Nevertheless, other important works are also introduced.

The information covered in this section relates to past technosignature SETI: targets of interest, observations to-date, data analysis pipelines, results to-date, and areas for further research. A total of 35 papers directly associated with BL

Table 2.1: BL TOIs: Target Selection

Survey	Type	Number
Isaacson et al. (2017)	Stars	1702
	Galaxies	123
Włodarczyk et al. (2020)	Stars	286,998
Czech et al. (2021)	Stars	26,000,000
Lacki et al. (2021)	Exotic	816

observations were reviewed with publication dates ranging from the program’s conception (2015) up until June of this year (2022). The results of this literature review were then used to define the research question stated in Section 1.2:

“Are there radio technosignatures hidden within past Breakthrough Listen Parkes observations? A search for narrowband drifting signals around *TESS* TOIs undergoing secondary transit.”

2.1.1 Targets of Interest

In the search for extraterrestrial life, it is logical to base our search around the ‘Goldilocks’ conditions that triggered abiogenesis, and continue to support life as we currently know it. While this logic motivates observations towards systems that provide such conditions (Czech et al., 2021), researchers have given due consideration to life that may thrive in more extreme environments by including a large number of exotic candidates for future observation (Lacki et al., 2021).

Over the last 5 years, BL have made strides towards the completion of their main science objectives as listed in Section 1.1.2. In their seminal target selection paper, Isaacson et al. (2017) state their intention to observe a list of 1702 main sequence and giant stars located within 50 pc of the Sun and 123 morphologically diverse galaxies located within 11 Mpc. Isaacson et al. (2017) also propose observations involving several types of exotic astrophysical objects/processes, and a sweeping observation that spans the entire Galactic plane. Since then, the list of nearby stellar targets for observation has grown dramatically to over 26 million (Włodarczyk et al., 2020; Czech et al., 2021), and a list of 816 exotic targets (Lacki et al., 2021) has been specified for future observation (see Table 2.1).

Table 2.2: BL TOIs: Observed & Analyzed

Study	Target/s	Facility	Band	Method
Enriquez et al. (2017b)	692 Stars	GBT	L	ON/OFF
Enriquez et al. (2019)	Ross 128	GBT	C	ON/OFF
Price et al. (2020)	1327 Stars	GBT/Parkes	L, S / 10cm	ON/OFF
Kumar et al. (2020)	Fomalhaut	Parkes	10cm	ON/OFF
Sheikh et al. (2021a)	Proxima Centauri	Parkes	UWL	ON/OFF
Sheikh et al. (2021b)	Proxima Centauri	Parkes	UWL	ON/OFF
Isaacson et al. (2018)	3 Stars	APF	374-950 nm	ON
Sheikh et al. (2020)	20 Stars	GBT	C	ON/OFF
Traas et al. (2021)	28 Stars	GBT	L, S, C, X	ON/OFF
Traas (2022)	28 Stars	GBT	L, S, C, X	ON/OFF
Franz et al. (2022)	61 Stars	GBT	L, S, C, X	ON/OFF
Gajjar et al. (2022)	1883 Stars	GBT	C	ON
Enriquez et al. (2018)	1I/‘Oumuamua	GBT	L, S, C, X	ON/OFF
MacMahon et al. (2018)	FRB121102	GBT	S, C	ON
Price et al. (2019a)	<i>BZ</i> ₅₀₉	Parkes	21cm	ON/OFF
Lipman et al. (2019)	Boyajian’s Star	APF	374-970nm	ON
Price et al. (2019b)	FRB180301	Parkes	21 cm	ON
Brzycki et al. (2019)	EPIC 249706694	GBT	C	ON/OFF
Perez et al. (2020)	Kepler 160	GBT	L, S, C	ON/OFF
Gajjar et al. (2021a)	PSR J1745–2900	GBT	C	ON
Gajjar et al. (2021b)	FRB20200120E	GBT	C	ON

Note: L = 1.15-1.73 GHz, S = 1.73-2.6 GHz, C = 3.95-8.0 GHz, X = 8.0-11.6 GHz, 10cm = 2.6-3.6 GHz, UWL = 0.704-4.032 GHz.

2.1.2 Past Observations

Archival data for hundreds of thousands of (mainly) stellar, galactic, extragalactic, and exotic observations has been collected by BL using both the Parkes and Green Bank radio telescopes, along with the Automated Planet Finder (APF) optical telescope over the past several years¹. Only a small portion of these data — relating to approximately 4000 stars — has been analyzed and published as of June 2022, offering a tremendous opportunity to analyze a subset of untouched observational data. A summary of published results is provided in Table 2.3, which lists the observing facilities, receivers, and methods associated with each target/set of targets.

¹A portion of this data is available publicly at: <https://breakthroughinitiatives.org/opendatasearch>. Breakthrough Listen intend to make all observational data available to the public.

2.1.3 Observing Techniques

BL’s main observing strategy for single target radio observations is centered around 30-minute observing sessions split into 6 consecutive 5-minute observing ‘cadences’. For each primary observing target (A), three nearby secondary targets (B, C, and D) are chosen from 40,000 of the brightest stars in the *Hipparcos* catalog (Perryman et al., 1997). These targets are then observed in the following pattern: ABACAD. This ON-source OFF-source method is effective in helping to identify and remove RFI; for if a signal appears in both the ON and OFF target observations, then it is not localized to the primary target and is thus terrestrial RFI (Lebofsky et al., 2019). As can be seen in Table 2.2, observation methods associated with the APF, fast transients (FRBs), and pulsars do not utilize the ON/OFF method, favoring long single target observations lasting anywhere between 15 and 30-minutes each. As this project is focused on single target ON/OFF radio observations, further discussion of optical, fast transient, and pulsar observations will be omitted.

2.1.4 Analysis Pipelines

In previous BL studies, two primary search codes have been used to analyze for technosignatures: TURBOSETI² (Enriquez & Price, 2019) and SPANDAK³. Each search algorithm is written in the PYTHON programming language and is publicly available as a downloadable set of scripts (packages) to be invoked by the user for data analysis. TURBOSETI specializes in the search for continuous narrowband drifting technosignatures, producing a set of stacked spectrograms (dynamic frequency plots) for each event that passes a specific set of input parameters, which are then visually inspected and compared to identify RFI and potential signals of interest (see Figures 3.3a, and 3.3b). SPANDAK, on the other hand, is designed to search for single or repeated radio pulses that have been either naturally or artificially dispersed (Gajjar et al., 2018, 2021b). This study made use of the TURBOSETI pipeline, the details of which will be discussed in Chapter 3.

²https://github.com/UCBerkeleySETI/turbo_seti

³<https://github.com/gajjarv/PulsarSearch>

Figure 2.1: A diagram depicting the flow of data during GBT/Parkes and APF observations/analysis. blc = compute node, bls = storage node, blpd = public data node. (Lebofsky et al., 2019).

2.1.5 Areas for Further Research

Several areas for further research were proposed throughout the set of reviewed literature, these include:

- An investigation into all existing BL data for non-thermal flare emission (Enriquez et al., 2019).
- An extended search of the *restricted* Earth Transit Zone, an area of the sky aligned with the ecliptic such that an observer in located within this zone would see Earth transiting the Sun (Sheikh et al., 2020).
- Observation and analysis of 186,780 Earth Transit Zone targets (Czech et al., 2021).

- Analysis of *TESS* targets which are serendipitously entering or exiting secondary transit during observation in search of signals that stop or start at these moments respectively (Franz et al., 2022).

Of these suggestions, I was particularly intrigued by the idea of analysing *TESS* TOIs — exoplanetary candidates — entering and exiting secondary transit. This suggestion ties SETI with exoplanet astronomy, an area in which the University of Southern Queensland’s astronomy department specializes. This suggestion heavily influenced the design of the research question to be addressed in this dissertation, which is once again:

“Are there radio technosignatures hidden within past Breakthrough Listen Parkes observations? A search for narrowband drifting signals around *TESS* TOIs undergoing secondary transit.”

2.2 Data Sets

2.2.1 List of Observed Targets

BL made 63,212 cadence observations between the dates 2018 January 24 and 2022 June 11 using the Parkes radio telescope. A full list of these targets was provided by project supervisor and BL’s Australian Project Scientist, Danny Price. This target list (see Table 2.3) includes information relating to the source name, observation start time, pointing offset, observation type, and observing campaign.

The naming conventions utilized by BL for each source are either descriptive — for example, including the coordinates of a galactic pointing — intuitive shorthand, or a source ID from various astronomical catalogues. Observation start times (see `Start_Unix` and `Start_UTC` in Table 2.3) are provided with both a Unix time stamp and Coordinated Universal Time (UTC) stamp following the format `YYYY-MM-DD_hhmmss`. The pointing offset of each observation (see `Pointing_Offset` in Table 2.3) describes the position of the source relative to the primary target; where S is the source target, R is a reference target, N is the

noise diode, and B1 through B12 refer to each beam that makes up the Parkes multibeam receiver. The observation type (see `Obs_Type` in Table 2.3) is marked as either `ON_OFF` (switching between a source and reference target as described in Section 2.1.3), `MB_TILE` (multibeam), `MB_SWITCHING` (switching beams for calibration), `UWL_SWITCHING` (switching modes for galactic centre observations), or `SINGLE_POINTING` (centred on a single target/area). Each observation was made as part of a particular observing campaign (see `Obs_Campaign` in Table 2.3). For the purposes of this project, we are only interested in `ON_OFF` observations of the stellar variety, with the end goal for this list being a set of observed *TESS* TOIs that underwent secondary transit.

2.2.2 Target Observations

There were only two observing campaigns that contain targeted stellar samples: the *TESS* and ISAACSON campaigns. Observations for the *TESS* and ISAACSON campaigns began in February 2020 and November 2018 respectively; both observing campaigns are still active and running to-date. The *TESS* campaign is quite self explanatory, in that it targets stars from the *TESS Input Catalogue* (*TIC*) that harbour exoplanets, the significance of which was discussed in Section 1.2.3. Unlike the *TESS* campaign, the ISAACSON campaign is not particularly focused on stars with exoplanets, but rather on observing every star located within 50 pc, mitigating the bias toward observing stars similar to our own Sun by incorporating stars of all spectral types. This campaign is a continuation of the original target list and observations presented in Isaacson et al. (2017) and Enriquez et al. (2017b) respectively.

The observational data for each target in both the *TESS* and ISAACSON campaigns was recorded using the Parkes Ultra-Wide-bandwidth Low-frequency (UWL) Receiver, which has a continuous frequency coverage of 704 to 4032 MHz (Hobbs et al., 2020). The observing session for each target lasted approximately 30-minutes, with a general observing cadence of 5-minutes ON-source (the target pointing) followed by 5-minutes OFF-source (a blank-sky reference pointing), following the pattern ON/OFF/ON/OFF/ON/OFF. The observational data from

Table 2.3: Truncated List of Targets Observed by BL using the Parkes Radio Telescope

	Source	Start_Unix	Start_UTC	Pointing_Offset	Obs_Type	Obs_Campaign
1	1934-638	1516773903	2018-01-24_060502	B1	MB_SWITCHING	CALIBRATOR
2	1934-638	1516774011	2018-01-24_060650	B2	MB_SWITCHING	CALIBRATOR
3	1934-638	1516774111	2018-01-24_060830	B3	MB_SWITCHING	CALIBRATOR
...
3586	G241.38+2.63	1522070263	2018-03-26_131742	N	MB_TILE	GALACTIC_PLANE
3587	G241.27+2.42	1522070616	2018-03-26_132335	N	MB_TILE	GALACTIC_PLANE
3588	G243.72+6.26	1522070991	2018-03-26_132950	N	MB_TILE	GALACTIC_PLANE
...
33285	1581645353	2020-02-14_015552	TIC 158297421	S	ON_OFF	<i>TESS</i>
33286	1581645703	2020-02-14_020142	TIC 158297421	R	ON_OFF	<i>TESS</i>
33287	1581646052	2020-02-14_020731	TIC 158297421	S	ON_OFF	<i>TESS</i>
...
63210	1654907742	2022-06-11_003541	HIP6414	R	ON_OFF	ISAACSON
63211	1654908092	2022-06-11_004131	HIP6414	S	ON_OFF	ISAACSON
63212	1654908439	2022-06-11_004718	HIP6414	R	ON_OFF	ISAACSON

Figure 2.2: BL Parkes Data Analysis Pipeline. Frequencies spanning 704 – 4032 HZ are captured by the Parkes UWL receiver, where the raw voltage data are split amongst 26 compute nodes (blc). Processing produces high frequency resolution data files which are analysed using the TURBOSETI pipeline to produce a set of files for each target.

each source and reference observation was split evenly into 128 MHz segments amongst the 27 compute nodes (26 and 1 spare) that make up the BL Parkes backend (Price et al., 2018, 2021) (see Figure 2.2). It is here that the raw voltage data from the UWL receiver was processed into high frequency resolution time-series data files using the BL-Parkes Data Recorder signal-processing system (Hobbs et al., 2020).

2.2.3 Target Data Files

The pre-processed archival data for each of the selected targets (see Section 3.2) was accessed remotely in the form of 3,500 HDF5 files through the Breakthrough Listen Data Centre (BLDC) located at the University of California, Berkeley. HDF5 files are used to store multidimensional arrays of scientific data. Each HDF5 file accessed through the BLDC contained dynamic high frequency resolution data (as detailed in Lebofsky et al. (2019)) ready to be analyzed using the TURBOSETI data analysis pipeline, the details of which will be explored in Chapter 3 Section 3.4.

2.2.4 Target System Information

Exoplanet detection via the transit method favors the discovery of short period, relatively large exoplanets due to the regular and pronounced troughs exhibited in stellar light curves. As the subset of targets selected for this study are all *TESS* candidates, they were all observed using the transit method, and thus exhibit planetary characteristics in line with the bias of their discovery method. The probability of observing a secondary transit event also favors exoplanets with short orbital periods; with the typical duration of BL ON/OFF observing sessions being approximately 30-minutes, transit events must happen within this short window of opportunity.

Table 6.1 of the Appendix lists notable parameters relating to each target observed in secondary transit. Note the short orbital periods, ranging from 0.513 to 17.468 days, with exoplanetary sizes ranging from 1.166 to 30.018 Earth radii

Figure 2.3: Four histograms illustrating the distribution of exoplanet orbital periods [top left], effective exoplanet temperatures [top right], exoplanet radii [bottom left], and stellar distances [bottom right] amongst the list of 25 eclipsing *TESS* TOIs.

(R_{\oplus}). Figure 2.3 (created using PYTHON package MATPLOTLIB⁴) illustrates the distribution of target exoplanet orbital periods, radii, effective temperature, and stellar distance. We can roughly gauge the habitability of our set of observed candidate exoplanets by exploring each of these histograms and categorizing them as either: Earth-like, Super-Earth, and Hot Jupiter. Earth-like planets have a similar mass and radius to that of Earth; Super-Earth’s are at least 2 times larger, and between 2 and 10 times more massive, than Earth; and Hot Jupiter’s have similar characteristics to Jupiter, with orbital periods under approximately 10 days. Studying Figure 2.3 we can see that the majority of observed TOIs have orbital periods between 1 and 10 days, with a set of radii that favors the presence of many Super-Earth and Hot Jupiter candidates.

⁴<https://matplotlib.org/>

The relationship between orbital period, orbital distance, and effective exoplanet temperature is evidenced in the distribution of exoplanets seen in Figure 2.3 and Table 6.1 of the Appendix. The lowest effective exoplanet temperature is given as 608 K, and the highest as 3536 K (see Table 2 of the Appendix), well above temperatures that would support and sustain the presence of liquid water and organic life. Nevertheless, we cannot rule out the potential for life that thrives in what we perceive as extreme conditions, nor the presence of transmitters either under the planetary surface, in spatial orbit, on the surface of a tidally locked moon.

All listings and table data utilized in this study have been made available in machine readable format at <https://doi.org/10.5846/tss> and <https://doi.org/10.586/dataset>, respectively.

Figure 2.4: Example narrowband drifting signal interrupted by secondary transit. Created using SETIGEN (Brzycki et al., 2022).

2.3 Simulated Signal of Interest

Figure 2.4 provides an example of a continuous narrowband drifting signal interrupted by secondary transit. This is an idealized scenario created using SETIGEN

(see Chapter 3 Section 3.1.3). As will be expanded upon in Section 3.4.3, an artificial narrowband signal originating from any particular celestial body would be expected to have a non-zero drift rate (due to the relative motions of the transmitting and receiving bodies), and appear explicitly in all ON-source and no OFF-source cadences (see Target_S and Target_R in Figure 2.4, respectively).

Note the gradual fade and cessation of the signal between $t = 400 - 500$ s; this represents the beginning of secondary transit as the transmitting body is eclipsed by its host (see Figure 1.2).

Chapter 3

Methodology

3.1 Resources & Software

3.1.1 Online Services

This project made heavy use of the NASA Astrophysics Data System¹ (NASA/ADS), the NASA Exoplanet Archive², the Transit and Ephemeris Service³, and SIMBAD⁴.

The NASA/ADS is an online portal designed specifically for researchers in physics and astronomy, providing users with an intuitive and convenient way to search through tens of millions of highly reputable scientific publications in one place (SAO/NASA, n.d.). The NASA/ADS was utilized consistently throughout this project to access all cited articles.

The NASA Exoplanet Archive is an online data service which provides access to, collates and compares stellar and exoplanetary catalogues in one convenient location. This archive was used to obtain a list of *TESS* project candidates from the 2021 TICv8.2 data release which was integral to the project target selection

¹NASA/ADS: <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/>

²NASA Exoplanet Archive: <https://exoplanetarchive.ipac.caltech.edu/cgi-bin/TblView/nph-tblView?app=ExoTbls&config=TOI>

³Transit and Ephemeris Service: <https://exoplanetarchive.ipac.caltech.edu/cgi-bin/TransitView/nph-visibletbls?dataset=transits>

⁴SIMBAD: <http://simbad.cds.unistra.fr/simbad/>

process (see Section 3.2). The NASA Exoplanet Archive also features many tools by which the user can query, view and manipulate particular catalogues and data sets. One such tool, the Transit and Ephemeris Service, was used to query the list of observed targets for secondary transit events, the results of which are supplied in Section 3.3.

Finally, SIMBAD, a dynamic astronomical database, was queried to cross-identify and return a list of alternative object identifiers to determine which of the observed targets had *TIC* identifiers, and were thus potential hosts to one or more *TESS* TOIs.

3.1.2 Computer Services

The entire data analysis process made use of all three BLDC high performance compute nodes located at BL’s headquarters at the University of California, Berkeley. Each Linux based compute node (denoted blpc0, blpc1, and blpc2) was accessed remotely via the secure shell protocol (SSH), which allows one computer to securely interface with another via a shared network connection. The data files used in this project were transferred from the BL Data Recorder at Parkes Observatory to the BLDC for analysis.

To make use of the PYTHON based TURBOSETI data analysis pipeline, a local PYTHON environment containing all prerequisite modules and packages was created, where the TURBOSETI commands could then be invoked from the terminal either directly, or by running a PYTHON file containing a TURBOSETI script. Complete analysis with TURBOSETI took approximately 300hrs of computing time split evenly over the three compute nodes. As BL’s compute nodes are a shared resource, analysis was spread out over a period of 1-2 months.

3.1.3 Software

This research has made use of the ALADIN SKY ATLAS⁵ (Bonnarel et al., 2000), TOPCAT⁶ (Taylor, 2005), TURBOSETI, and SETIGEN⁷(Brzycki, 2022).

⁵ALADIN SKY ATLAS: <https://aladin.u-strasbg.fr/>

⁶TOPCAT: <http://www.star.bris.ac.uk/~mbt/topcat/>

⁷SETIGEN: <https://github.com/bbrzycki/setigen>

The ALADIN SKY ATLAS is an interactive sky map for the visualization of astronomical targets and survey images. The ALADIN SKY ATLAS is available in two modes, as a: web widget called Aladin Lite (Boch & Fernique, 2014) specializing in the simple sky visualizations, and as a regular application called ALADIN DESKTOP. This project made use of ALADIN DESKTOP (v11.024), as it provided the tools and functions necessary to map the complete list of *TESS* targets observed by BL using Parkes, with the added utility to highlight and label those targets that underwent secondary transit (see Figure 3.1).

TOPCAT is an interactive viewing, editing, and analysis tool for tabular data. TOPCAT (v4.8-6) was used to sort, cross match, and merge several lists of targets and their metadata throughout the target selection process (see Section 3.2).

TURBOSETI is a PYTHON package specially designed to search filterbank data files for continuous narrowband drifting signals. Filterbank files are a special storage format for binary data relating to the dynamic power spectra recorded during each BL observation⁸ (Lebofsky et al., 2019). TURBOSETI (v2.3.2) was used extensively in the data analysis process, the details of which are supplied in Sections 3.4.1 and 3.4.2.

SETIGEN is a PYTHON package specially designed to create and insert custom, artificial narrowband signals into either authentic or generated radio frequency data. In this project, SETIGEN (v2.3.2) was used to generate an example of a continuous drifting narrowband signal as it would be expected to look if it were interrupted by the beginnings of secondary transit.

3.2 Target Selection

To determine which of the observed stellar targets were host to *TESS* TOIs (exoplanetary candidates), a list containing the source ID of each observed target was first uploaded to, and queried by, SIMBAD to obtain their respective *TESS* Input Catalogue identifiers. Those targets without *TIC* identifiers were removed

⁸For more on working with filterbank files, see: [https://github.com/UCBerkeleySETI/breakthrough/blob/master/GBT/filterbank_tutorial/Filterbank%20Tutorial%20\(public\).ipynb](https://github.com/UCBerkeleySETI/breakthrough/blob/master/GBT/filterbank_tutorial/Filterbank%20Tutorial%20(public).ipynb)

from the observed target list by cross-matching the obtained list of *TIC* targets with the observed target list using TOPCAT. This list of observed *TIC* targets was then cross-matched with a list of *TESS* TOIs accessed through the NASA Exoplanet Archive⁹. This comparison was done, once again, using TOPCAT by cross-matching the *TIC* ID columns of both lists, resulting in 1599 observed *TESS* TOIs. This list of 1599 targets was then further reduced by removing those targets whose exoplanetary candidature was based on either false positives (attributed to other astrophysical interactions such as binary star systems) or false alarms (from instrumental systematics) as listed in the NASA Exoplanet Archive; leaving a list of 1474 *TESS* TOIs whose disposition was either confirmed, previously known, or needing confirmation.

The final step for this list of observed *TESS* TOIs was to determine those which underwent secondary transit during observation by passing either the secondary ingress or egress Schelling points (see Figure 1.2). To achieve this, the list of observed *TESS* TOIs was uploaded to the NASA Exoplanet Archive Transit and Ephemeris Service form with an observing window that encompassed both observing campaigns (2019/02/13 to 2022/06/10). This returned a large list detailing every secondary transit midpoint event that occurred for each target over the specified observing window. The produced list of *TESS* TOIs and their respective transit midpoints was then cross-matched with the list of *TESS* TOIs and their respective observation start times using TOPCAT, returning an enormous list containing all possible combinations of secondary transit midpoints and observation start times. To determine the approximate time of secondary ingress and egress, the known transit duration of each TOI was obtained from the NASA Exoplanet Archive, halved, and either added to (egress) or subtracted from (ingress) each respective target's observed secondary transit midpoint.

This list of observed *TESS* TOIs, their respective observation times, and their times of ingress and egress were loaded into a PYTHON dataframe using the PANDAS (v1.0.3)¹⁰ PYTHON package, and manipulated with a simple python

⁹*TESS* Project Candidates: <https://exoplanetarchive.ipac.caltech.edu/cgi-bin/TblView/nph-tblView?app=ExoTbls&config=TOI>

¹⁰PANDAS PYTHON package: <https://pandas.pydata.org/>

algorithm (see Listing 1 of the Appendix) to return the rows of any targets whose observation start time was within ± 30 -minutes (the typical duration of a BL observing session) of their respective ingress or egress events. Each observation was then manually checked to ensure enough time had elapsed either side of the event window to have captured the exoplanet in both full view and occultation. This produced a final target list of 30 *TESS* TOIs that underwent secondary transit during BL Parkes observations (see Table 3.1).

3.3 List of Targets

Each of the 30 *TESS* TOIs discussed above is listed in Table 3.1 along with their celestial coordinates, observation start times, and estimated times of secondary ingress and egress. Figure 3.1 projects the distribution of all 1474 observed *TESS* TOIs (white plus symbols) on a skymap overlaid with the positions of each of the 30 unique *TESS* targets with exoplanetary candidates that underwent secondary transit (green circles). Of the listed 30 targets, 26 are unique, leaving four observed *TESS* targets with either multiple TOIs, or TOIs that were observed multiple times. TIC 440887364 and TIC 260647166 are associated with two and four unique *TESS* TOIs respectively; where the TOIs associated with TIC 80166433 and TIC 370133522 were observed to be in secondary transit twice (see Table 3.1).

Unfortunately during the data analysis process, it was found that the data files relating to *TESS* target TIC 251852984 were corrupt, reducing the total number of unique observed targets to 25. It was also found that the data associated with sub-band 30 (3648–3776 MHz) for all observations was missing; this is taken into account in the discussion of results (see Chapter 4).

3.4 Data Analysis

Data Analysis was split into three parts; the first two (see Sections 3.4.1 and 3.4.2) made use of BL’s TURBOSETI pipeline, and the third (see Section 3.4.3) involved the visual inspection and characterization of TURBOSETI output.

Table 3.1: *TESS* TOIs that Underwent Secondary Transit During Parkes Observations

Target Name	TOI	RA (h/m/s)	DEC (d/m/s)	Observation Start Time (JD)	Secondary Ingress (JD)	Secondary Egress (JD)
TIC 118327533	346.01	00h41m22.68s	-37d20m34.87s	2459675.646	2459675.65	
TIC 130924120	757.01	12h31m58.76s	-35d33m16.03s	2459244.299	2459244.314	
TIC 134200185	500.01	07h06m14.18s	-47d35m16.14s	2459079.278	2459079.291	
TIC 183985250	193.01	23HDF54m40.53s	-37d37m41.61s	2458894.8		2458894.818
TIC 220016044	357.01	02h09m17.25s	-48d29m05.06s	2459047.463	2459047.479	
TIC 230982885	195.01	01h38m25.23s	-55d46m19.2s	2458903.774		2458903.789
TIC 251852984	323.01	00h32m48.66s	-32d03m33.9s	2459047.23	2459047.248	
TIC 260304296	187.01	06h18m27.73s	-57d00m48.6s	2459310.689	2459310.696	
TIC 260647166	1233.01-4	12h26m17.78s	-51d21m46.99s	2459090.461		2459090.443
TIC 280206394	677.01	09h36m28.65s	-50d27m47.13s	2459564.435		2459564.44
TIC 299799658	1062.01	02h32m29.03s	-78d01m25.26s	2459236.87	2459236.877	
TIC 31268146	1948.01	05HDF52m17.12s	-70d55m13.11s	2459559.261	2459559.262	
TIC 317060587	1052.01	22h30m02.47s	-75d38m47.62s	2459205.854		2459205.857
TIC 33911302	341.01	23h43m22.8s	-23d59m52.88s	2459020.489	2459020.497	

TIC 351601843	1075.01	20h39m53.09s	-65d26m58.92s	2459458.226	2459458.235	
TIC 370133522	1078.01	20h27m42.88s	-56d27m44.23s	2458977.225		2458977.233
				2459458.162		2459458.168
TIC 371443216	1924.01	09HDF50m19.22s	-66d06m50.13s	2459600.208		2459600.223
TIC 380589029	1084.01	17HDF55m33.77s	-61d44m50.64s	2458997.203		2458997.213
TIC 38509907	722.01	04h09m31.1s	-62d51m02.36s	2459096.426	2459096.439	
TIC 402026209	232.01	23h34m15.1s	-42d03m42.4s	2459186.929		2459186.934
TIC 440887364	836.01	15h00m19.17s	-24d27m15.13s	2458965.111		2458965.121
	836.02					
TIC 70524163	2421.01	02h12m36.97s	-35d23m27.3s	2459559.042	2459559.045	
TIC 80166433	1125.01	19HDF53m09.05s	-46d22m11.97s	2459143.889	2459143.9	
				2459147.027		2459147.028

Figure 3.1: A skymap pinpointing the location of every *TESS* TOI observed by BL using the Parkes radio telescope (white plus symbols). *TESS* TOI that underwent secondary transit during observation are labeled and circled in green. This figure was created using the ALADIN SKY ATLAS.

A total of 3,650 HDF5 data files amounting to 20 TB of data were accessed remotely through the BLDC located at the University of California, Berkeley (see Section 3.1.2). Due to the sheer volume of data to be analyzed; the resource intensive analysis pipeline that is TURBOSETI; and the time restricted nature of this research project, data analysis was performed using the computing resources of all three high-powered compute nodes available through the BLDC. TURBOSETI functions can be invoked either directly on the BLDC Linux based command line, or by opening and executing a custom PYTHON script on said command line.

I chose to write a custom PYTHON script based on the examples provided in the TURBOSETI github, the TURBOSETI documentation¹¹ (Breakthrough Listen, 2022a), and BL’s Parkes Multibeam ‘Data and Technical Tutorial’ (Breakthrough Listen, 2022b). Creating a custom PYTHON TURBOSETI script allowed for the automation of functions that needed to be repeated for each set of target data files (the full script of which is available in Appendix Listing 2). GPU accelerated TURBOSETI analysis took approximately 13 hours per target, amounting to 312 hours of total compute time. The total time spent running TURBOSETI was reduced to approximately 104 hours by utilizing all three compute nodes simultaneously.

TURBOSETI is a package of PYTHON scripts containing several classes, each with an array of modules that perform a number of dependent and independent functions when called. The TURBOSETI analysis pipeline followed in this study can be broken down into three stages (see Figure 3.2):

1. Hit Search: searches the dynamic high frequency resolution data contained within each HDF5 file for continuous narrowband drifting signals. Each signal identified by TURBOSETI in this stage is known as a ‘hit’.
2. Event Search: searches for hits that occur in all ON-source cadences in an observing session, and not in any OFF-source pointings. This is done to filter out RFI from terrestrial sources, which can generally be seen regardless of telescope pointing. Groups of related hits that pass this test

¹¹TURBOSETI Documentation: <https://turbo-seti.readthedocs.io/en/latest/contents.html>

are called ‘events’.

3. Event Plot: creates a set of stacked spectrograms (also known as a waterfall plot with time and frequency axis) for each identified event.

Figure 3.2: TURBOSETI Analysis Pipeline

3.4.1 TURBOSETI Hit Search

To perform each hit search, the TURBOSETI class ‘FINDDOPPLER’ was invoked as an object in a custom PYTHON script. This class allows the user to specify search parameters relating to the: minimum/maximum signal drift rate (change in signal frequency due to relative radial motion), the minimum signal to background noise ratio (S/N), and the number of coarse channels (frequency sub-bands) in which to divide and search each HDF5 data file.

In this study, I chose a non-zero *minimum* drift rate of 0.1 Hz/s. This decision was based on the calculated fractional drift rate of Earth (due to both rotation and orbital motion) of 0.11 nHz/s as reported by Sheikh et al. (2019). At observing frequencies of 1 GHz, this equates to a drift rate of 0.11 Hz/s (note that this value is in Hz, not nHz), providing a reasonable value for the minimum doppler drift that may affect an incoming signal. Drift rates below 0.11 Hz/s *are* possible if Earths orbital and/or rotational motion are opposite in radial direction to those of the source, as this would effectively correct a portion of the Doppler shift; yet the targets being observed in this study have very short orbital periods, and are thus expected to have associated drift rates higher than 0.1 Hz/s.

According to (Gajjar et al., 2021a), a *maximum* drift rate of 4 Hz/s is deemed sufficient to detect a signal transmitted from the surface of an Earth-sized exoplanet. The exoplanets targeted in this study are a mix of super Earths, gas

giants, and hot Jupiters (see Table 6.1 of the Appendix), most of which have orbital periods of less than 10 days (see Figure 2.3). Again, such short orbital periods reflect truly phenomenal orbital velocities, which could cause a signal drift rate far greater than those estimated for Earth-sized exoplanets. Sheikh et al. (2019) recommend a maximum normalized drift rate of approximately 200 nHz/s (or 200 Hz/s at an observing frequency of 1 GHz) for future SETI technosignature searches; yet this would be computationally expensive and time intensive. For the scope of this project, particularly time constraints, a maximum drift rate of 4 Hz/s was adopted in line with Traas et al. (2021); Gajjar et al. (2021a); Smith et al. (2021); Gajjar et al. (2021a), with the potential to increase and reanalyze at a later date.

A minimum S/N value of 10 was selected in line with the lowest S/N value used by BL to date (Price et al., 2020; Perez et al., 2020; Sheikh et al., 2020; Traas et al., 2021; Gajjar et al., 2021a). A S/N value of 10 means that a narrowband signal would have to be at least 10 times stronger than the accompanying background radio noise to be flagged as a hit. Finally, the number of coarse channels — the number of subdivisions for each 128 MHz segment — was set to a value of 32, allowing TURBOSETI to search for hits in 6 MHz bandwidths.

For every cadence file that underwent a FindDoppler search, TURBOSETI created two new files: a data file containing detailed information about each hit in a comma delimited tabular data format, and a log file containing highlights from the terminal output.

3.4.2 TURBOSETI Event Search & Plot

Once the initial hit search was complete, TURBOSETI’s `FIND_EVENT_PIPELINE` class was invoked. This class checks for related hits in each set of observing cadence data files that satisfy the user defined `FILTER_THRESHOLD` parameter. The `FILTER_THRESHOLD` can be set to an integer value between 1 and 3, where 1 searches for hits above a set signal to noise ratio (does not perform an ON/OFF check); 2 searches for hits that are in some ON-source cadence observations; and 3 searches for hits that are in all ON-source cadence observations. For the purposes

of this project, a filter threshold of 2 would be ideal as the target may be hidden from view in some ON-source cadences due to secondary transit; yet due once again to computing and time constraints, a filter threshold of 3 was selected, reducing the number of detected events by a factor of up to 10,000.

The dynamic frequency information for each event in the set of cadences was then stored by TURBOSETI'S `FIND_EVENT_PIPELINE` in a comma delimited .csv file, where the `PLOT_EVENT_PIPELINE` class was invoked to plot the data for each event as a set of stacked spectrograms and saved as an image in portable network graphic (PNG) format for visual inspection and characterization.

3.4.3 Dynamic Spectra Inspection

Once the TURBOSETI hit search, event search and event plot analysis was complete, each waterfall plot was visually inspected for signals of interest and RFI. Figures 3.3 and 3.3b provide examples of two waterfall plots that passed the TURBOSETI analysis pipeline in past BL studies (Traas et al., 2021; Sheikh et al., 2021a). Figure 3.3a features a narrowband drifting signal in both the ON (TIC 281731203) and OFF (HIP53072) source observations, and is thus *not* localized to TIC 281731203, meaning that it must be a moving source of local RFI such as a plane or satellite. Figure 3.3b also features a narrowband drifting signal, yet this time the signal is only present in the ON-source cadences (ProxCen). This candidate signal of interest, dubbed BLC1, was eventually determined to be RFI originating from an unknown local source.

Nevertheless, the discovery of such an interesting signal spurred the design of a Technosignature Verification Framework (Sheikh et al., 2021a) for continuous narrowband technosignatures observed with single-dish telescopes. The Technosignature Verification Framework is as follows:

1. Verify the functionality of instrumentation.
2. Check for the signal's presence in reference observations at a lower S/N ratio.
3. Check for local catalogued sources of RFI at the same frequency as the

(a) A waterfall plot displaying the dynamic spectra for each cadence. Note that the drifting signal presents in both ON (TIC 281731203) and OFF (HIP53072) source observations, indicating that this signal does not originate from the source target, and is a result of terrestrial RFI (Traas et al., 2021).

(b) A waterfall plot for candidate signal BLC1. Note the presence of a drifting signal in each ON source observation, and the lack of signal in the OFF source, reference observations (Sheikh et al., 2021a).

Figure 3.3: Example Waterfall Plots from Past Studies

signal of interest.

4. Compare any changes in signal drift rate over time to the known drift rate patterns of human-made technology.
5. Compare any changes in signal drift rate over time to the drift rates and periods expected in the target system.
6. Check for the presence of the signal in archival data.
7. Search other frequencies in the same observation for similar signals. If found, check for characteristics of RFI.
8. Assess whether any signals found in steps 6 and/or 7 are generated by the same process as the signal.
9. If signals found in steps 6 and/or 7 *are* generated by the same process as the signal of interest, assess for RFI and perform steps 1 through 8.
10. Observe the target again with both the same observatory/instrumentation, and other observatories/instrumentation, in an attempt to re-detect the signal.

Any signals that pass the TURBOSETI analysis pipeline and visual inspection are to be verified using the steps in this framework.

Chapter 4

Results

The aim of this study was to analyze a subset of data from archival BL Parks observations for artificial, continuous narrowband drifting signals. The presence of such a signal would potentially indicate the presence of a technologically advanced civilization.

Data analysis was performed in two parts; the first made use of TURBOSETI and its classes FINDDOPPLER, FIND_EVENT_PIPELINE, and PLOT_EVENT_PIPELINE; and the second involved the visual inspection and characterization of TURBOSETI output.

4.1 Results of TURBOSETI Analysis

A total of 3650 high frequency resolution HDF5 data files were analyzed using TURBOSETI'S FINDDOPPLER class for continuous narrowband signals with a minimum drift rate of ± 0.1 Hz/s, a maximum drift rate of ± 4 Hz/s, and a minimum signal to noise ratio of 10. With these parameters in place, FINDDOPPLER flagged a total of 1,954,880 hits to be analyzed using TURBOSETI'S FIND_EVENT_PIPELINE class for hits that were present in all ON-source cadences for each respective observing session. Of the 1,954,880 detected hits,

14,639 were identified as events, being present in all respective ON-source cadences and no OFF-source cadences (at the same S/N). The `TURBOSETI PLOT_EVENT_PIPELINE` class was then used to plot the dynamic frequency data from each set of cadences involved in the event, producing a total of 14,639 .png image files to be visually inspected.

Figure 4.1: A histogram showing the distribution of hits (narrowband signals above a S/N ratio of 10 with drift rates lying between ± 0.1 and $\pm 4.0 Hz/s$) and events (hits present in all related ON-source cadences) found during TURBOSETI analysis.

Figure 1.1 provides an overview of the common sources of local RFI that regularly impact observations made using the Parkes UWL receiver (Hobbs et al., 2020). A strong correlation between sources of local RFI and the number of hits detected using TURBOSETI can be seen when comparing respective frequencies in Figure 4.1 to Figure 1.1. It is was expected that most — if not *all* — of the detected hits were attributable to local sources of RFI. A full list of targets with their respective number of hits and events is available in Table 2 of the Appendix.

4.2 Visual Analysis

The validity of each event was scrutinized by individually inspecting each of the 14,639 waterfall plots produced during TURBOSETI analysis. Each waterfall plot (see Figure 4.2) contains a set of stacked spectrograms corresponding to the set of cadences for each observing session at a specific frequency. Note that, for each waterfall plot:

- The name of the target is listed at the top of the image,
- Underneath the target name lies the calculated drift rate ν . (Hz/s), and the starting time of the first observation in MJD format,
- The names of the targets observed in each cadence are in the top left of each spectrogram, in order (ABACAD) from top to bottom, The Y axis represents time (s) running from top (0s) to bottom (1800s),
- The X axis represents frequencies (kHz) relative to a central frequency (MHz),
- To the right of the image is a normalized power scale, the colours of which represent the signal to noise ratio of every pixel in the plot,
- There lies a red dashed line representing the calculated drift rate and predicted position of signal (as calculated in TURBOSETI).

4.2.1 Clear Examples of RFI

Figures 4.2a through 4.2d feature several types of signal and signal groupings that appeared continuously throughout inspection. These signals were all easily identifiable as local RFI due to their presence in both the ON and OFF-source cadences. Figure 4.2a features two prominent narrowband signals emitting at a central frequency of approximately 3625 MHz. The first of these signals has a vertical sinusoidal drift rate evolution (signal drift rate over time), suggesting frequency modulated signal emission from a non-moving local source; whereas the second signal is vertical (suggesting no drift rate at all) and linear, varying in power over the observing session. According to Figure 1.1 and the Australian

Communications and Media Authority (ACMA) search register¹, both of these signals are likely associated with Australia’s National Broadband Network (NBN) operating locally in the Parkes area.

Figure 4.2b features a ‘noisier’ background, accompanied by a set of vertical, linear narrowband signals and one sinusoidal in nature. These signals are all found around the central frequency of 1161 MHz, and according to CSIRO’s RFI Frequency List² are likely associated with operations of the Australian Department of Defence.

Figure 4.2c features an assortment of strong and weak diagonal signals at a central frequency of approximately 1576 MHz. This constant drift rate suggests a moving source of emission. A slightly broader signal shows a geometry that curves over time, suggesting a drift rate that is changing over time. According to Figure 1.1, this central frequency lies within the realm of satellites, aligning with observations of several moving sources of emission.

Figure 4.2d features a peculiar moving signal at a central frequency of about 3430 MHz that changes drift rate dramatically over the course of the 30-minute observation. Whilst Figure 1.1 would suggest that this signal lie well within the realm of the NBN, this signal does not exhibit the regularity and zero drift rate expected of NBN emission. The spurious nature of this signal is likely due to emission from a moving vehicle, such as an aeroplane passing over the beam of the Parkes telescope.

¹ACMA: https://web.acma.gov.au/rrl/register_search.search_dispatcher

²CSIRO ATNF RFI Frequency List: https://www.parkes.atnf.csiro.au/observing/rfi/parkes_rfi_survey/frequency_list.html

Figure 4.2: Four waterfall plots exhibiting several types of RFI regularly encountered during visual inspection of TURBOSETI output. Figure (a) features two prominent narrowband signals: one with a linear drift rate evolution and one sinusoidal. Figure (b) presents a set of 7 narrowband signals at quite a noisy frequency; 6 linear and 1 sinusoidal in drift pattern. Figure (c) is quite busy, with one wider curved signal accompanied by several diagonal signals of varying strength. Figure (d) features a very narrow signal whose drift rate pattern varies over time. For an explanation on the likely origins of each signal and their respective shapes, see Section 4.2.

Figure 4.3: Two waterfall plots exhibiting the ambiguous RFI events encountered during visual inspection of TURBOSETI output. Figures (a) and (b) both show one narrowband signal with a diagonal drift rate evolution. Both signals are prominent in all ON-source cadences, yet either carry over into, or are slightly visible in, the OFF-source (`_R`) cadences.

4.2.2 Notably Ambiguous RFI

Figure 4.3 features two waterfall plots, each with a narrowband signal whose RFI origin was, at first glance, ambiguous. Both signals have a constant drift rate, and feature prominently in the ON-source cadence observations. Upon closer inspection, it can be seen that both signals either carry-over into the reference cadences, or feature weakly in a lower S/N environment.

Chapter 5

Discussion

This study focused on a technosignature search toward relatively nearby stars (≤ 745 pc) with either candidate, confirmed, or known exoplanets as listed in the *TESS* catalogue. As of May 2022, BL has observed 1474 of these exoplanetary systems (see Figure 3.1), many of which have been observed several times over. This sample size — much too large for the scope of this project — was reduced to 25 by selecting only those with exoplanets that began or finished secondary transit during observation. This allowed for the analysis of data from two Schelling points, and for the exploration of a potential signal interruption event due to exoplanetary eclipse.

Data analysis using TURBOSETI took approximately 300hrs of compute time on the compute nodes linked to the BLDC. A total of 1,954,880 narrowband signals were detected with TURBOSETI'S FINDDOPPLER pipeline to be above a S/N of 10, with drift rates ranging between ± 0.1 and ± 4.0 Hz/s, respectively. Of these narrowband hits, 14,639 passed the TURBOSETI FIND_EVENT_PIPELINE, with a narrowband signal featuring in all ON-source cadences. TURBOSETI analysis was followed by several hours of visual analysis, inspecting each of the 14,639 event waterfall plots for a signal of interest. Of the plethora of continuous narrowband drifting signals encountered during the visual inspection, none were attributable to anything other than human-made RFI. This was not an unexpected outcome.

The search for extraterrestrial intelligence is an incredibly ambitious goal —

even more so if we remove the anthropocentric assumptions we tend to make about habitability, technology, and means of long distance communication. Nevertheless, these assumptions provide us with a foundation upon which to begin our search for other life in the Universe, intelligent or otherwise.

Whilst no signals of interest were found in this particular study, a new search method has been introduced which incorporates information from known exoplanet ephemeris in the search for technosignatures that would indicate the presence of extraterrestrial intelligence; and the analysis techniques utilized in this study can be applied to other areas of astronomy in search of narrowband, continuous, or periodic signals. For each set of data that is analyzed for technosignatures — no matter the sample size, waveband, S/N ratio, drift rate, or epoch — we take one step closer to understanding our place in the cosmos.

5.1 Figures of Merit

In line with past BL SETI studies, one metric along with two Figures of Merit (FM) have been calculated to compare the efficiencies and effectiveness of this study to past and future SETI studies (see Table 5.1 and Table 2 of the Appendix).

5.1.1 Equivalent Isotropic Radiated Power

The minimum Equivalent Isotropic Radiated Power ($EIRP_{min}$) metric describes the minimum amount of power required to transmit a detectable omni-directional signal of a particular central frequency from a transmitter with the equivalent size and capabilities of the receiving telescope (Enriquez et al., 2017b). Each $EIRP_{min}$ value was calculated using the following equation (Enriquez et al., 2017b):

$$EIRP_{min} = 4\pi d^2 F_{min}, \quad (5.1)$$

where d is the distance to the target (m), and F_{min} is the minimum detectable flux (Wm^{-2}). Following to Price et al. (2020), the minimum detectable flux for a narrowband signal can be calculated using:

$$F_{min} = \frac{S_{min}}{\delta\nu}, \quad (5.2)$$

where S_{min} is the minimum flux density, and $\delta\nu$ is the bandwidth of the transmitting signal. Finally, the minimum flux density for a narrowband signal is given by (Enriquez et al., 2017b):

$$S_{min} = S/N_{min}SEFD\sqrt{\frac{\delta\nu}{n_{pol}\tau_{obs}}}, \quad (5.3)$$

where S/N_{min} is the minimum signal to noise ratio, n_{pol} is the number of polarisations, τ_{obs} is the observing time (s), and $SEFD$ is the System Equivalent Flux Density. The SEFD describes the sensitivity of the radio observation as a function of system noise and the effective collecting area of the receiving telescope. Hobbs et al. (2020) list a set of median SEFD values for each sub-band of the Parkes UWL receiver, with a minimum value of 33 Jy (1 Jy = 10^{-26} W m⁻² Hz⁻¹) at a central frequency of 1664 MHz — this is the value that was used for the SEFD in this study. As for the other parameters, S/N_{min} was set to a value of 10 (the S/N ratio used during TURBOSETI analysis), n_{pol} to 2 (as the UWL receiver records over two polarisation channels), τ_{obs} to 300 seconds (equivalent to an observing cadence of 5-minutes), and $\delta\nu$ to unity (in line with Enriquez et al. (2017b)).

The minimum EIRP value calculated for each target system is listed in Table 2 of the Appendix, encompassing values between 1.2195×10^{12} and 8.9486×10^{14} W, inclusive. To put these values into context, the energy released by the Hiroshima bomb in 1945 was approximately 6.7×10^{13} J¹. Thus, to send and maintain an isotropic, detectable signal of equivalent strength to those listed in Table 2 of the Appendix would mean harnessing and directing the energy released by an atomic bomb *every second*.

¹For more information see: <https://www.world-nuclear.org/information-library/safety-and-security/non-proliferation/hiroshima,-nagasaki,-and-subsequent-weapons-testin.aspx>.

5.1.2 Continuous Waveform Transmitter Figure of Merit

The first FM to be calculated was the Continuous Waveform Transmitter Figure of Merit (CWTFM). The CWTFM is a metric designed by BL to standardize and compare the efficacy of past and future BL SETI surveys with regard to the volume of space searched in each project (Margot et al., 2021). Each CWTFM value was calculated as follows (Enriquez et al., 2017b):

$$CWTFM = \zeta_{AO} \frac{EIRP_{min}}{N_{stars} \nu_{rel}}, \quad (5.4)$$

where N_{stars} is the total number of stars — equal to the number of pointings ($N_{pointings}$) multiplied by the number of stars (n_{stars}) per pointing; ν_{rel} is the fractional bandwidth — equal to the total bandwidth ($\Delta\nu_{tot}$) divided by the central frequency (ν_c) of the survey; and ζ_{AO} is a normalization factor based on the now-retired Arecibo Observatory, providing a standard by which each study can be compared.

This metric was designed to compare SETI *surveys*. This study is not a survey and contains outlying targets that would skew results, yet it is worth calculating such a value to be compared to relevant future studies. Rather than presenting a single CWTFM value representing the entire study, I have calculated a minimum CWTFM value ($CWTFM_{min}$) using parameters from the nearest target where $N_{stars} = 1$ and $EIRP_{min} = 1.2195 \times 10^{12} W$, as well as a maximum CWTFM value ($CWTFM_{max}$) incorporating parameters from the furthest target where $N_{stars} = 25$ and $EIRP_{min} = 8.9486 \times 10^{14} W$.

A value of $5 \times 10^{-11} W^{-1}$ was calculated for ζ_{AO} using the EIRP, ν_{rel} , N_{stars} , and CWTFM values given in Enriquez et al. (2017b). ν_{rel} was set to a value of 1.9231 using a $\Delta\nu_{tot}$ value of 3200 MHz and a ν_{mid} value of 1664 MHz. Values 31.2 and 925.6 were calculated for $CWTFM_{min}$ and $CWTFM_{max}$, respectively. A full list of target specific CWTFM values are available in Table 2 of the Appendix.

5.1.3 Drake Figure of Merit

The second and final FM to be calculated was the Drake Figure of Merit (DFM). The DFM quantifies and combines several dimensions of parameter space searched in a study for comparison with other technosignature SETI studies (Margot et al., 2021). The DFM was calculated using the following equation from (Margot et al., 2021):

$$DFM = \frac{\Delta\nu_{tot}\Omega}{F_{det}^{3/2}}, \quad (5.5)$$

where $\Delta\nu_{tot}$ is the total observed bandwidth (3200 MHz as above), Ω is the total angular area of sky covered during all 25 observations (measured in deg^2), and F_{det} is the minimum detectable flux. Values Ω and F_{det} are specific to the telescope from which each observation was made and must be calculated using separate equations.

Firstly, Ω is calculated by multiplying the Full Width Half Maximum (FWHM) of the telescope beam by the number of targets observed in the study. The FWHM tells us the angular area of the telescope beam where the amount of light received from a source is half its maximum value. The FWHM of the Parkes telescope was calculated using the following equation (Hobbs et al., 2020):

$$FWHM = \frac{1.02\lambda}{D} \quad (5.6)$$

where λ is the wavelength being observed, and D is the diameter of the telescope. From this equation, you can see that the value for the FWHM varies with wavelength, which is equal to $\lambda = c/\nu$ — ν being frequency, and c being the speed of light. For this calculation, I will use the central frequency of the UWL at 1664 MHz for the value of ν , and 2.9979×10^8 m/s for c , equating to a λ of 0.1802 m. As the diameter of the Parkes telescope is 64 m, the value for the FWHM at an observing frequency of 1664 MHz is 0.0029 rad², leading to a value for Ω of $25 \times FWHM = 0.0718rad^2$ or 235.6529 deg².

Secondly, the minimum flux detectable by Parkes telescope was calculated

using the following equation (Price et al., 2020):

$$F_{det} = S/N_{min}SEFD\sqrt{\frac{B}{n_{pol}t_{obs}}} \quad (5.7)$$

where S/N_{min} is the minimum signal to noise threshold, $SEFD$ is the system equivalent flux density, B is the channel bandwidth, n_{pol} is the number of recorded polarizations, and t_{obs} is the integration time. As mentioned previously, a S/N_{min} value of 10 was used in this study, along with a $SEFD$ value of 33 Jy. Parkes records with a channel bandwidth of $B = 2$ Hz, over two polarizations ($n_{pol} = 2$) and each observation took approximately 300-seconds ($t_{obs} = 300$). Together, this equates to a F_{det} of 19.0526 Jy. Finally, plugging these values in to the DFM equation 5.5 gives a result of $1.4080 \times 10^{37} \text{ GHz } m^3 \text{ W}^{-3/2}$.

5.1.4 Recent Study Comparison

The values for the Equivalent Isotropic Radiated Power, Continuous Waveform Transmitter Figure of Merit, and Drake Figure of Merit in this study were compared to two of the most recent and relevant BL publications involving a technosignature search toward *TESS* TOIs (see Table 5.1). Franz et al. (2022) and Traas (2022) selected their stellar targets from the *TESS Input Catalogue*, with the shared goal of examining *TESS* TOIs for radio technosignatures using the GBT's L, S, C, and X-band receivers (1 - 11 GHz combined bandwidth). Franz et al. (2022) and Traas (2022) observed 61 and 28 *TESS* TOIs with a total of 66 and 113 cadences, respectively. Each cadence was analyzed for using the TURBOSETI pipeline for narrowband signals above a S/N threshold of 10, and maximum drift rates within $\pm 4 \text{ Hz/s}$. While neither studies returned a signal of interest, they did provide metrics and FM to be compared to those from studies such as this.

It must be noted that lower CWTFM values are favorable as such results reflect a lower power requirement for signal transmission, and/or a higher number of targets surveyed; while a larger DFM is preferred as this value reflects the amount of parameter space searched.

Table 5.1 presents the $EIRP_{min}$, $CWTFM$, and DFM values calculated for this study alongside those published by Franz et al. (2022) and Traas (2022) (if available). The majority of targets that were analyzed in this study were located within 300 pc (see Figure 2.3 and Table 6.1 of the Appendix) with a few distant outliers, thus Table 5.1 includes values for both the nearest (TIC 440887364 at approximately 28 pc) and farthest (TIC 118327533 at approximately 745 pc) targets. A full list of individual $EIRP_{min}$ and $CWTFM$ values is available in Table 2 of the Appendix.

Table 5.1: A Comparison of the Figures of Merit with *TESS* SETI Studies Published in 2022.

Study	Receiver	$EIRP_{min}$ [W]	$CWTFM$	DFM [GHz m ³ W ^{3/2}]
This Study:				
TIC 440887364	UWL	1.2195×10^{12}	31.2	1.408×10^{37}
TIC 118327533	UWL	8.9486×10^{14}	925.6*	1.408×10^{37}
Traas (2022)	L	4.90×10^{14}	1995	
	S	-	2038	-
	C	-	1878	-
	X	-	4675	-
Franz et al. (2022)	L	1.67×10^{14}	3793	2.10×10^{32}
	S	3.93×10^{14}	2828	-
	C	7.88×10^{14}	3060	-
	X	7.19×10^{14}	3686	-

*This is the maximum possible $CWTFM$ value for this study. See Section 5.1.3 for details.

The $EIRP_{min}$ and $CWTFM$ values published by Franz et al. (2022) and Traas (2022) are based on the most distant target (936 and 880 pc respectively) in each survey, reporting $EIRP_{min}$ values within a few times $10^{14}W$ and $CWTFM$ values between 1995 and 4675 for observations using the GBT's L, S, C, and X-band receivers. Comparatively, this study produced an $EIRP_{min}$ and $CWTFM_{max}$ of $8.9486 \times 10^{14}W$ and 925.6 for the most distant target (745 pc), with 1.2195×10^{12} and 31.2 for the closest target (28 pc) analyzed. The major difference in FM results stems from the large bandwidth of the GBT observations.

This study reports a DFM of $1.408 \times 10^{37} \text{ GHz m}^3 \text{ W}^{3/2}$. While Traas (2022) does not report a DFM value for their study; this value, if calculated, would equate to approximately 3 times that of Franz et al. (2022)'s $2.10 \times 10^{32} \text{ GHz m}^3$

$W^{3/2}$, as the only difference in the parameters used to calculate this value relate directly to the number of targets observed using the GBT. Regardless, the DFM calculated in this study far exceeds the values presented in Franz et al. (2022) and Traas (2022). It might be expected that studies utilizing the GBT — with its larger diameter and bandwidth — would be considered more effective than those utilizing Parkes, yet the DFM penalizes larger telescopes like the GBT for having smaller fields of view.

5.2 Research Question

In this study, it was my aim to address the following research question:

“Are there radio technosignatures hidden within past Breakthrough Listen Parkes observations? A search for narrowband drifting signals around *TESS* TOIs undergoing secondary transit.”

Following the analysis of 25 *TESS* TOIs using BL’s TURBOSETI pipeline, it can be stated that there was no sign of any narrowband signal within the range of frequencies covered by the Parkes UWL receiver (704 – 4032 MHz) above a S/N ratio of 10 with a drift rate between ± 0.1 and ± 4.0 Hz/s. This does not rule out the potential for extant signals of interest at a lower S/N threshold, wider range of drift rates, transmitting at a different set of frequencies, at a different epoch.

It must be stated that while the motivation behind the pursuit of such targets undergoing secondary transit stems from the idea of strategically advantageous orbital positions (Schelling points) in which to transmit a technosignature, it has also served as a means to reduce the *TESS* TOI sample size to an subset of targets appropriate for the scope of this dissertation. Regardless of the negative results produced in this study, the idea of signal interruption due to exoplanet eclipse can and should be explored further, as will be discussed in Section 6.1 of the Conclusions.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

In this dissertation, I have analyzed the archival observational data of a set of 25 nearby (≤ 745 pc) stellar targets with transiting exoplanets for artificial narrow-band radio signals that would indicate the presence of extraterrestrial intelligence.

This set of 25 stellar targets was selected from a list of 63,212 observations made by Breakthrough Listen (BL) using the CSIRO Parkes 64-m radio telescope, Murriyang, between 2018 January 24 and 2022 June 11. As this study was particularly interested in searching for technosignatures toward transiting exoplanets, the list of 63,212 target observations was cross-matched with the exoplanetary hosts listed in the *TESS Input Catalogue (TIC)* to return a list of 1474 targets (see Figure 3.1). This list was further reduced using NASA Exoplanet Archive's Transit Ephemeris Service Form, returning the final set of 25 targets that underwent secondary transit during observation.

Observations were made using the Parkes UWL receiver, covering a frequency range of 704 - 4032 MHz inclusive. The data for each observation was split into 26×128 MHz segments and processed into high frequency resolution data files. Each set of target data files was analyzed using BL's TURBOSETI pipeline for narrowband signals with a minimum S/N ratio of 10, minimum drift rate of ± 0.1 Hz/s, and maximum drift rate of ± 4.0 Hz/s.

Of the 1,954,880 narrowband signals (hits) flagged during analysis, 14,639

were identified as events (being present in all respective ON-source target observations) and were subsequently plot as a set of 14,639 waterfall plots. Each plot was visually inspected for a signal of interest by comparing signals present in related source and reference cadences, yet each event was attributable to terrestrial RFI.

6.1 Future Work

We are, I hope, at the very beginnings of humanity’s journey of self discovery — a journey that may one day take us to stars and perhaps civilizations beyond our own. In the mean time, SETI can help us bridge these vast, impassable distances by exploring the Universe for signs of technology that may infer the presence of other intelligent civilizations. While still predominantly privately funded, the resources available to undertake SETI research are steadily growing. With the addition of observing time at facilities such as China’s Five-hundred-meter Aperture Spherical radio Telescope (FAST) (Zhang et al., 2020), South Africa’s 64 antenna MeerKAT radio telescope array (Cox et al., 2020); and near-future facilities of unparalleled sensitivity such as Australia’s Square Kilometer Array (SKA) and the next generation of the Very Large Array (ngVLA), the future of radio SETI is bright.

An ever-growing trove of archival data is at the ready for technosignature analysis, yet the sheer volume and influx of this data will increasingly outpace data analysis methods like that used in this study. The future of SETI relies on the development of analysis methods centred around artificial intelligence and machine learning, many studies of which are currently underway.

With regard to this work, neither the analyzed data set nor the targets involved should be forgotten, but re-analyzed at a broader range of frequencies, S/N ratios, drift rate parameters, and epochs. The idea of signal interruption due to exoplanet occultation should be further explored with regard to signal of interest verification and as a means for detecting weak signals via the stacking of observational data at the point of secondary ingress and egress, which may also mitigate the presence of inconsistent RFI.

Bibliography

- Baum, S. D., Haqq-Misra, J. D., & Domagal-Goldman, S. D. 2011, *Acta Astronautica*, 68, 2114, doi: [10.1016/j.actaastro.2010.10.012](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2010.10.012)
- Boch, T., & Fernique, P. 2014, in *Astronomical Society of the Pacific Conference Series*, Vol. 485, *Astronomical Data Analysis Software and Systems XXIII*, ed. N. Manset & P. Forshay, 277
- Bonnarel, F., Fernique, P., Bienaymé, O., et al. 2000, , 143, 33, doi: [10.1051/aas:2000331](https://doi.org/10.1051/aas:2000331)
- Borucki, W. J., Koch, D., Basri, G., et al. 2010, *Science*, 327, 977, doi: [10.1126/science.1185402](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1185402)
- Breakthrough Listen. 2022a, turbo_seti, texadactyl. <https://turbo-seti.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>
- . 2022b, Data and Technical Tutorial, Breakthrough Listen. http://seti.berkeley.edu/parkes_mb/overview.html
- Brzycki, B. 2022, bbrzycki/setigen: v2.3.1, v2.3.1, Zenodo, Zenodo, doi: [10.5281/zenodo.6410676](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6410676)
- Brzycki, B., Siemion, A., Croft, S., et al. 2019, *Research Notes of the American Astronomical Society*, 3, 147, doi: [10.3847/2515-5172/ab4bd6](https://doi.org/10.3847/2515-5172/ab4bd6)
- Brzycki, B., Siemion, A. P., de Pater, I., et al. 2022, *The Astronomical Journal*, 163, 222
- Cocconi, G., & Morrison, P. 1959, , 184, 844, doi: [10.1038/184844a0](https://doi.org/10.1038/184844a0)

- Cox, T., Czech, D., & MacMahon, D. 2020, in American Astronomical Society Meeting Abstracts, Vol. 235, American Astronomical Society Meeting Abstracts #235, 212.03
- Czech, D., Isaacson, H., Pearce, L., et al. 2021, , 133, 064502, doi: [10.1088/1538-3873/abf329](https://doi.org/10.1088/1538-3873/abf329)
- Drake, F. D. 1961, *Physics Today*, 14, 40, doi: [10.1063/1.3057500](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3057500)
- . 1965, in *In Current aspects of exobiology*, 323–345
- Drake, F. D. 1979, *Cosmic Search*, 1, 10
- Enriquez, E., & Price, D. 2019, turboSETI: Python-based SETI search algorithm, *Astrophysics Source Code Library*, record ascl:1906.006. <http://ascl.net/1906.006>
- Enriquez, J. E., Siemion, A., Croft, S., et al. 2017a, in *Radio Exploration of Planetary Habitability (AASTCS5)*, Vol. 49, 300.03
- Enriquez, J. E., Siemion, A., Foster, G., et al. 2017b, , 849, 104, doi: [10.3847/1538-4357/aa8d1b](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aa8d1b)
- Enriquez, J. E., Siemion, A., Lazio, T. J. W., et al. 2018, *Research Notes of the American Astronomical Society*, 2, 9, doi: [10.3847/2515-5172/aaa6c9](https://doi.org/10.3847/2515-5172/aaa6c9)
- Enriquez, J. E., Siemion, A., Dana, R., et al. 2019, *International Journal of Astrobiology*, 18, 33, doi: [10.1017/S1473550417000465](https://doi.org/10.1017/S1473550417000465)
- Evans, J. E., & Maunder, E. W. 1903, , 63, 488, doi: [10.1093/mnras/63.8.488](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/63.8.488)
- Franz, N., Croft, S., Siemion, A. P. V., et al. 2022, , 163, 104, doi: [10.3847/1538-3881/ac46c9](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/ac46c9)
- Gajjar, V., Siemion, A. P. V., Price, D. C., et al. 2018, , 863, 2, doi: [10.3847/1538-4357/aad005](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aad005)
- Gajjar, V., Perez, K. I., Siemion, A. P. V., et al. 2021a, , 162, 33, doi: [10.3847/1538-3881/abfd36](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/abfd36)

- Gajjar, V., Michilli, D., Faber, J. T., et al. 2021b, *Research Notes of the American Astronomical Society*, 5, 166, doi: [10.3847/2515-5172/ac157a](https://doi.org/10.3847/2515-5172/ac157a)
- Gajjar, V., LeDuc, D., Chen, J., et al. 2022, , 932, 81, doi: [10.3847/1538-4357/ac6dd5](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ac6dd5)
- Hall, R., & King, L. J. 1992, in *IEEE Antennas and Propagation Society International Symposium*, 862–865, doi: [10.1109/APS.1992.221814](https://doi.org/10.1109/APS.1992.221814)
- Halpern, P., & Tomasello, N. 2016, *Advances in Astrophysics*, 1, 135, doi: [10.22606/adap.2016.13001](https://doi.org/10.22606/adap.2016.13001)
- Harrison, A. 2011, *Astropolitics*, 9, 63, doi: [10.1080/14777622.2011.557619](https://doi.org/10.1080/14777622.2011.557619)
- Hobbs, G., Manchester, R. N., Dunning, A., et al. 2020, , 37, e012, doi: [10.1017/pasa.2020.2](https://doi.org/10.1017/pasa.2020.2)
- Isaacson, H., Siemion, A. P. V., Marcy, G. W., et al. 2018, *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*, 131, 014201, doi: [10.1088/1538-3873/aaeae0](https://doi.org/10.1088/1538-3873/aaeae0)
- Isaacson, H., Siemion, A. P. V., Marcy, G. W., et al. 2017, , 129, 054501, doi: [10.1088/1538-3873/aa5800](https://doi.org/10.1088/1538-3873/aa5800)
- Jeffery, M. H. 1964, *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 116, 62, doi: [10.1111/j.1749-6632.1964.tb33939.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-6632.1964.tb33939.x)
- Kerins, E. 2021, , 161, 39, doi: [10.3847/1538-3881/abcc5f](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/abcc5f)
- Kumar, P., Price, D. C., Deller, A. T., Gajjar, V., & Shannon, R. M. 2020, *Research Notes of the American Astronomical Society*, 4, 99, doi: [10.3847/2515-5172/aba11d](https://doi.org/10.3847/2515-5172/aba11d)
- Lacki, B. C., Brzycki, B., Croft, S., et al. 2021, , 257, 42, doi: [10.3847/1538-4365/ac168a](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4365/ac168a)
- Lebofsky, M., Croft, S., Siemion, A. P. V., et al. 2019, , 131, 124505, doi: [10.1088/1538-3873/ab3e82](https://doi.org/10.1088/1538-3873/ab3e82)

- Lipman, D., Isaacson, H., Siemion, A. P. V., et al. 2019, , 131, 034202, doi: [10.1088/1538-3873/aafe86](https://doi.org/10.1088/1538-3873/aafe86)
- MacMahon, D. H. E., Price, D. C., Lebofsky, M., et al. 2018, , 130, 044502, doi: [10.1088/1538-3873/aa80d2](https://doi.org/10.1088/1538-3873/aa80d2)
- Margot, J., Pinchuk, P., Geil, R., et al. 2021, in American Astronomical Society Meeting Abstracts, Vol. 53, American Astronomical Society Meeting Abstracts, 230.08
- Ohara, W. M., Pastana, M., & Camelier, P. 2022, Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society, doi: [10.1093/zoolinnea/zlac026](https://doi.org/10.1093/zoolinnea/zlac026)
- Oliver, B. M. 1973, , 19, 425, doi: [10.1016/0019-1035\(73\)90118-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0019-1035(73)90118-8)
- Perez, K., Brzycki, B., Gajjar, V., et al. 2020, Research Notes of the American Astronomical Society, 4, 97, doi: [10.3847/2515-5172/ab9f36](https://doi.org/10.3847/2515-5172/ab9f36)
- Perryman, M. A. C., Lindegren, L., Kovalevsky, J., et al. 1997, , 323, L49
- Price, D. C., MacMahon, D. H. E., Lebofsky, M., et al. 2018, , 35, e041, doi: [10.1017/pasa.2018.36](https://doi.org/10.1017/pasa.2018.36)
- Price, D. C., Croft, S., DeBoer, D., et al. 2019a, Research Notes of the American Astronomical Society, 3, 19, doi: [10.3847/2515-5172/ab010b](https://doi.org/10.3847/2515-5172/ab010b)
- Price, D. C., Foster, G., Geyer, M., et al. 2019b, , 486, 3636, doi: [10.1093/mnras/stz958](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stz958)
- Price, D. C., Enriquez, J. E., Brzycki, B., et al. 2020, , 159, 86, doi: [10.3847/1538-3881/ab65f1](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/ab65f1)
- Price, D. C., MacMahon, D. H. E., Lebofsky, M., et al. 2021, Research Notes of the American Astronomical Society, 5, 114, doi: [10.3847/2515-5172/ac00c1](https://doi.org/10.3847/2515-5172/ac00c1)
- Ricker, G. R., Winn, J. N., Vanderspek, R., et al. 2014, in Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, Vol. 9143, Space Telescopes and Instrumentation 2014: Optical, Infrared, and Millimeter Wave, ed. J. Oschmann, Jacobus M., M. Clampin, G. G. Fazio, & H. A. MacEwen, 914320, doi: [10.1117/12.2063489](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2063489)

- SAO/NASA. n.d., Astrophysics Data System, Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory. <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/>
- Sheikh, S. Z., Siemion, A., Enriquez, J. E., et al. 2020, *The Astronomical Journal*, 160, 29, doi: [10.3847/1538-3881/ab9361](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/ab9361)
- Sheikh, S. Z., Wright, J. T., Siemion, A., & Enriquez, J. E. 2019, , 884, 14, doi: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab3fa8](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab3fa8)
- Sheikh, S. Z., Smith, S., Price, D. C., et al. 2021a, *Nature Astronomy*, 5, 1153, doi: [10.1038/s41550-021-01508-8](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41550-021-01508-8)
- Sheikh, S. Z., Smith, S., Price, D., et al. 2021b, *Research Notes of the American Astronomical Society*, 5, 248, doi: [10.3847/2515-5172/ac33b2](https://doi.org/10.3847/2515-5172/ac33b2)
- Shostak, S. 2021, Drake Equation, SETI Institute. <https://www.seti.org/drake-equation-index>
- Smith, S., Price, D. C., Sheikh, S. Z., et al. 2021, *Nature Astronomy*, 5, 1148, doi: [10.1038/s41550-021-01479-w](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41550-021-01479-w)
- Tarter, J. 2001, , 39, 511, doi: [10.1146/annurev.astro.39.1.511](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.astro.39.1.511)
- Tarter, J. C., Agrawal, A., Ackermann, R., et al. 2010, in *Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series*, Vol. 7819, *Instruments, Methods, and Missions for Astrobiology XIII*, ed. R. B. Hoover, G. V. Levin, A. Y. Rozanov, & P. C. W. Davies, 781902, doi: [10.1117/12.863128](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.863128)
- Taylor, M. B. 2005, in *Astronomical Society of the Pacific Conference Series*, Vol. 347, *Astronomical Data Analysis Software and Systems XIV*, ed. P. Shopbell, M. Britton, & R. Ebert, 29
- Traas, R. 2022, in *American Astronomical Society Meeting Abstracts*, Vol. 54, *American Astronomical Society Meeting Abstracts*, 233.01
- Traas, R., Croft, S., Gajjar, V., et al. 2021, *The Astronomical Journal*, 161, 286, doi: [10.3847/1538-3881/abf649](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/abf649)
- Westby, T., & Conselice, C. J. 2020, , 896, 58, doi: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab8225](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab8225)

Włodarczyk, B. S., Garrett, M. A., & Siemion, A. P. V. 2020, , 498, 5720, doi: [10.1093/mnras/staa2672](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa2672)

Worden, P. 2016, in 67th International Astronautical Congress 2016, 34378

Worden, S. P., Drew, J., Siemion, A., et al. 2017, Acta Astronautica, 139, 98, doi: [10.1016/j.actaastro.2017.06.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2017.06.008)

Zhang, Z.-S., Werthimer, D., Zhang, T.-J., et al. 2020, , 891, 174, doi: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab7376](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab7376)

Appendix

Listings and table data have been made available in machine readable format at <https://doi.org/10.5846/tss> and <https://doi.org/10.586/dataset>, respectively.

```
1 # Imports Pandas python package to be invoked using 'pd'.
2 import pandas as pd
3
4 # Loads data from csv file into Pandas dataframe (df).
5 df = pd.read_csv("../.../Documents/MS8002/Parkes/
6 Targets_Start_Ing_Eg.csv")
7
8 # Queries the original dataframe (df) to see which values in
9 the Ingress_JD column are within +/- 30-minutes (+/- 0.02083
10 JD) of their respective start_jd values.
11 df = df.query("Ingress_JD - 0.02083 < start_jd < Ingress_JD +
12 0.02083")
13
14 # Creates a new dataframe (df_Ingress_Matches) to store
15 specific values from matches in the previous line.
16 df_Ingress_Matches = pd.DataFrame().assign(TIC_ID=df["TIC_ID"
17 ], Planet_Name=df["Planet_Name"], Start_JD=df["start_jd"],
18 Ingress_JD=df["Ingress_JD"])
19
20 # Saves the above information from the df_Ingress_Matches
21 dataframe to a csv file.
22 df_Ingress_Matches.to_csv("Ingress_Matches.csv")
23
24 # Restart Kernal to refresh data stored in original daraframe
25 (df).
26
27 # Repeats the same process for egress values.
```

```

17     df = df.query("Egress_JD - 0.02083 < start_jd < Egress_JD +
18     0.02083")
19     df_Egress_Matches = pd.DataFrame().assign(TIC_ID=df["TIC_ID"],
20     Planet_Name=df["Planet_Name"], Start_JD=df["start_jd"],
21     Egress_JD=df["Egress_JD"])
22     df_Egress_Matches.to_csv("Egress_Matches.csv")

```

Listing 1: The PYTHON Script Created for the Calculation of Secondary Ingress & Egress Events.

```

1     import time
2     import glob
3     from turbo_seti.find_doppler.find_doppler import FindDoppler
4     from turbo_seti.find_event.find_event_pipeline import
5     find_event_pipeline
6     from turbo_seti.find_event.plot_event_pipeline import
7     plot_event_pipeline
8
9     HDF5DIR = "/datag/users/username/TIC_ID/blcXX/"
10    DATDIR = "/datax/scratch/username/TIC_ID/blcXX/"
11    OUT_DIR = "/datax/scratch/username/TIC_ID/blcXX"
12
13    # --- DOPPLER SEARCH --- #
14    # -- Create list of all HDF5 files in directory.
15    HDF5filelist = sorted(glob.glob("/datag/users/username/TIC_ID
16    /blcXX/*.HDF5")) #CHANGE
17    print("There are %i HDF5 files in this directory." % len(
18    HDF5filelist))
19
20    # -- Loop through all .HDF5 files in HDF5DIR.
21    t1 = time.time()
22    for i in range(len(HDF5filelist)):
23        print("\nInstantiating the FindDoppler object.")
24        fdop = FindDoppler(datafile=HDF5filelist[i],
25                            max_drift=4,
26                            min_drift=0.1,
27                            n_coarse_chan=32,
28                            snr=10,
29                            gpu_backend=True,
30                            out_dir=OUT_DIR)

```

```

27     # -- Search for hits that satisfy the above parameters.
28     print("\nBegin doppler search. Please wait ...")
29     fdop.search()
30     # -- Report elapsed time.
31     elapsed_time = time.time() - t1
32     print("\nDoppler search complete. Elapsed time = {} seconds".
33     format(elapsed_time))
34
35     # --- EVENT SEARCH & PLOT --- #
36     # -- Create list of all .dat files in directory.
37     datfilelist = sorted(glob.glob(DATDIR + "*.dat"))
38     print("There are %i .dat files in this directory." % len(
39     datfilelist))
40     # -- Writes .dat files into a .lst, as required by
41     find_event_pipeline.
42     with open(DATDIR + "datfiles.lst", "w") as f:
43         for item in datfilelist:
44             f.write("%s\n" % item)
45     # -- Writes HDF5 files into a .lst, as required by
46     find_event_pipeline.
47     with open(DATDIR + "HDF5files.lst", "w") as f:
48         for item in HDF5filelist:
49             f.write("%s\n" % item)
50     # -- Instantiate find_event_pipeline and search for events.
51     print("\nFinding events.")
52     CSVSPATH = DATDIR + "m4_f3_snr10.csv"
53     find_event_pipeline(dat_file_list_str=DATDIR + "datfiles.lst"
54     ,
55     HDF5_file_list_str=DATDIR + "HDF5files.
56     lst",
57     filter_threshold=3,
58     number_in_cadence=len(datfilelist),
59     user_validation=False,
60     saving=True,
61     csv_name=CSVSPATH)
62     print("\nEvent search complete.")
63     # -- Plot events.
64     print("\nPlotting events.")
65     plot_event_pipeline(event_csv_string=CSVSPATH,

```

```

60         fils_list_string=DATDIR + "HDF5files.lst"
        ,
61         plot_dir=DATDIR)
62     print("\nPlotting events complete.")

```

Listing 2: The PYTHON Script Created to Run the TURBOSETI Pipeline.

Table 1: Observed Secondary Transit *TESS* TOI System Information

Target Name	TOI	Orbital Period (d)	Exoplanet Rad. (R_{\oplus})	Exoplanet Temp. (K)	Stellar Dist. (pc)
TIC 118327533	346.01	8.282	30.018	1027	745.217
TIC 130924120	757.01	17.468	2.117	608	60.342
TIC 134200185	500.01	0.548	1.166	1617	47.392
TIC 183985250	193.01	0.792	4.720	1978	80.437
TIC 220016044	357.01	0.940	6.615	3123	480.322
TIC 230982885	195.01	2.073	12.670	1555	151.068
TIC 260304296	187.01	0.513	15.071	3536	184.529
TIC 260647166	1233.01	3.795	1.586	1099	64.598
	1233.02	6.204	2.068	932	64.598
	1233.03	14.176	2.720	708	64.598
	1233.04	19.592	3.120	636	64.598
TIC 280206394	677.01	11.237	13.110	1252	141.812
TIC 299799658	1062.01	4.113	2.265	1077	82.173
TIC 31268146	1948.01	3.648	2.330	2903	219.482
TIC 317060587	1052.01	9.140	3.063	1007	129.804
TIC 33911302	341.01	1.814	11.581	923	415.551
TIC 351601843	1075.01	0.605	1.720	1336	61.459
TIC 370133522	1078.01	0.518	1.193	1089	49.056
TIC 371443216	1924.01	2.824	17.100	2100	170.696
TIC 380589029	1084.01	1.349	15.640	2166	494.182
TIC 38509907	722.01	15.300	2.397	519	57.685
TIC 402026209	232.01	1.338	14.810	1700	267.206
TIC 440887364	836.01	8.596	2.640	704	27.502

	836.02	3.817	1.693	704	27.502
TIC 70524163	2421.01	4.347	10.400	1534	327.927
TIC 80166433	1125.01	1.546	-	1634	237.593

Table 2: Individual Target TURBOSETI Results & Figures of Merit

Target Name	Hits	Events	$EIRP_{min}$ (W)	CWTFM
TIC 118327533	28524	181	8.9486×10^{14}	33731.5530
TIC 130924120	30518	278	5.8042×10^{12}	218.7894
TIC 134200185	21807	159	3.56152×10^{12}	134.2516
TIC 183985250	389148	225	1.0319×10^{13}	388.9589
TIC 220016044	37492	253	3.7147×10^{14}	14002.5220
TIC 230982885	406119	384	3.6762×10^{13}	1385.7270
TIC 260304296	30744	336	5.5180×10^{13}	2080.0187
TIC 260647166	30451	310	6.7279×10^{12}	4440.7636
TIC 280206394	35730	3523	3.2424×10^{13}	1222.2210
TIC 299799658	23580	2781	1.0887×10^{13}	410.3761
TIC 31268146	30084	1661	7.7667×10^{13}	2927.6665
TIC 317060587	26011	227	2.7165×10^{13}	1024.000
TIC 33911302	23326	150	2.7841×10^{14}	10494.7590
TIC 351601843	29258	307	6.0899×10^{12}	229.5592
TIC 370133522	205328	131	3.8799×10^{12}	146.2541
	35207	299	3.8799×10^{12}	146.2541
TIC 371443216	27793	223	4.6977×10^{13}	1770.8039
TIC 380589029	172139	180	3.9374×10^{14}	14842.1780
TIC 38509907	32809	281	5.3650×10^{12}	202.2319
TIC 402026209	29696	250	1.1512×10^{14}	4339.2653
TIC 440887364	237015	342	1.2195×10^{12}	31.2000
TIC 70524163	27844	247	1.7338×10^{14}	6535.4898
TIC 80166433	25829	164	9.1013×10^{13}	3430.7658
	18428	1747	9.1013×10^{13}	3430.7658